

The New 21st Century World Order

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Radical positions are often inspired by "absolute certainty" (a common situation regarding civil society organizations, without legally formalized public responsibilities, environmental issues and certain minorities, often interconnected) or by the interests of the powerful, formulators and interpreters of the new law.

We can see it this month with the absolute failure of the Climate Summit this month, after two-week meeting ended without a crucial agreement in Madrid and the popular phenomena of the phenomena of the teenage activist Greta Thunberg.

Global themes are already a reality we have to live with and, in many cases, but not always, until we accept them as correctly motivated.

However, this does not mean accepting as certain some debatable measures desired or imposed by great powers, such as the definition of immense natural areas as a "heritage of humanity", possibly compromising the right of peoples to freely dispose of their wealth (as defined by in the Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, UN, 16/1211966),

The "sins" committed in the past by the US, as they were or are the destruction of forests and indigenous peoples and atmospheric pollution, do not constrain or inhibit them.

Finally, they tend to divide the world into two blocks separated by the gap in development, resulting in disturbing tensions and conflicts in the name of the good World Order.

This new international physiognomy, distinct from that prevailing in the colonial and imperial centuries and in the balance of power game in Europe and also distinct from the more recent physiognomy of the Yalta, Bretton Woods and nuclear terror world, makes the principles, the instruments and practices that have reduced and controlled, or attempted to reduce and control international "anarchy" in the past until recently, begin to show their shortcomings for today's realities.

It is in this process that the dilution of the idea of national sovereignty, the multi centuries, fruit of post-Middle Age absolutist centralization, thrives on the emergence of nationalisms, natural or "artificially" cultivated by States.

On the other hand, the still imprecise idea of restricted sovereignty grows more oriented considered as global or critical by the major powers, for which the coincidence of sovereignty with national borders would be obsolete.

It is worth remembering, however, that the challenge of Iraq was answered with the modern version of the oldest instrument of international politics, - violence.

The old instrument may no longer suffice (rarely, it was), but it is not yet necessary: the cure against violence remains dependent on a superior force!

The current lack of direction, by allowing both readjustments under the prevailing economic focus, and the resurrection of nationalisms drowned out by the security imperatives of global confrontation.

Of course, no political, economic and social system is unchanging and they have changed even by radical disruption.

It is preferable to make them change respecting the right of peoples to self-determination that may have to adapt to the evolution of the world (applies to the right to natural resources), but not "run over" by the arrogance of power and the enthusiasm of utopia.

In short: we live in a time of appreciation of the unity of mankind and this climate tends to emphasize new legal schemes of global validity.

As an example of this type of problem, it is worth mentioning the concept of global ecological security, which intends to justify world rules of environmental conduct on the basis of the understanding of the great powers on the subject - understanding predominantly sincere, but not always immune to their interests.

Another concept that deserves attention is that which seeks to make respect for national sovereignty upon respect for human rights; indeed, it deserves attention not for the merit of human rights, absolutely fair, but for the fact that the judgment of that merit will depend essentially on the understanding of the one more powerful.

The policy of the United States it is to regulate their external relations in function of the practice of the democracy. This is a strange policy not because of the merit of democracy, which is the right ideal, but again because the judgment of merit will be unilateral and depend on the interests of the more powerful.

All this international evolution has been, until now still discretely and imprecisely, embedded in the assembly of what is conventionally called the New International Order, to be controlled by the powerful oligarchy, under the leadership of the United States, which the collapse of the Soviet empire left behind free, with military capability for the actual uncontained world

This situation is, in fact, semi-resulting from the immense technological-military capacity of the United States and semi-consented by the major powers that share

common interests and values with them and that rely on the US military power to defend them.

This hegemonic power at a given moment always seeks to extend, complete and (or) consolidate its hegemony over every universe of interest.

After the Cold War, which legitimized the division of the world between two hegemonies, is natural that the United States now try to extend the order that seems appropriate to the new times.

They will strive to maintain unquestionable military supremacy and strive to construct a system of planetary control sufficiently loose that it does not injure fundamental susceptibilities of the other major powers, but is capable of handling the issues regarded as critical.

Some major partners are governments like Israel and Saudi Arabia, and others under the preponderant influence of the United States.

Thus, it may be expected that, sooner or later, the pressure of revisionist pretensions will eventually shake the current situation in which the United States plays a "more equal" role in the major powers as a whole.

Except for strongly structured hypothesis (China, Islamic unity), it is likely that the first concussions will certainly not radically heretical shakes - occur at the hands of Germany, Israel and Japan.

It is natural, therefore, that these powers, impelled by roles consistent with their immense economic and technological capabilities, will assert their hegemonies in Europe and Asia Pacific also in the field of security.

One should not rule out the "resurrection" of a great Russian power, in (perhaps Confederate) configuration closer to Russia the power of Peter the Great, than of the great socialist homeland of Lenin, which will exert a strong influence in eastern Europe in the Balkan countries and Asia as it has exercised in recent centuries.

And for sure it will exercise it with the enthusiastic support of the former Soviet military who, like all the military in the world, are more interested in their homeland and its power implications than in serving an ideology.

The relative economic decline of the United States vis-à-vis Japan and Europe, in addition to reactivating US nationalist protectionism, contrary to its liberal rhetoric and damaging relations with other rich countries, puts the United States at risk of having its hegemony founded especially in military power, turning them (perhaps with England) into a militarized country in the service of the New Order, as has happened in the Gulf

War, whose huge financial account was heavily supported by Japan, Israel, Germany and Saudi Arabia. .

In this context, the United States' intention to maintain the present status of sole superpower, with conventional military power capable of deterring and defeating any veil of direct challenge to its important interests, is clearly symptomatic.

In addition, although in the 1980s the atom had "lost ground" as the major powers sought to revitalize the political-strategic flexibility of their conventional forces, the nuclear weapon remains the last unquestionable instance and in this instance the states United States will enjoy unreachable persuasive supremacy, although nuclear terror helps the weakest in cost-effectiveness,

We are living in this 21st century the emergence of a New International Order that, at least from what can be inferred so far and can be foreseen for the short term future, will not eliminate the factors of disturbance and international contradictions and will not be fairer or fairer more democratic and peaceful than was the historical past.

We live the emergence of a New Order built through the sum of changes, some inexorable and widely agreed upon and others desired and imposed by power.

This is not a rapid and radical revolution, as the French and Russian revolutions intended to extend to the world, but it is undoubtedly a "reform" sensitive to its depth, influenced by the inequality in the power structure and, similarly, than in the cold war, which was undermined by the reduction of national liberty in matters admitted as critical - the defense of the West and now the internationalized environment, human and minority and other rights.

The new order under construction tends to preserve an international model that defines distinct levels of transparent international rights and responsibilities in the rules of the Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty.

Will the formerly force-sleeping autonomist Impacts (Yugoslavia, Czechoslovakia, and the former Soviet Union) stimulate other similar claims (e.g. Catalan vs. Spain, Northern Irish, and Scottish vs. England)?

Is the Western European model viable in the less developed world whose national economies depend on trade with the rich world, with no resources to compensate for gaps and subsidies, without hegemonic poles capable of overcoming the disintegrating forces (United States for Canada and Mexico Japan to some Asian countries and Germany to Europe, if "bearable" for France and England), without a common political-strategic threat and where some regional rivalries were "patrolled" by the Cold War superpowers, but were not extinguished?

Can the exercise of democracy, which is adequate to obtain from the Society support for a foreign policy level to conciliation with concessions, overcome the effects of historical antagonisms and present asymmetries?

Will Portugal "assimilate" the Spanish economic invasion? Is France subjected to growing German hegemony in Europe?

The second major trend in international politics is the subject of this very brief observation.

It is the gradual transfer in the axis of world tensions from the practically extinct East-West ideological political confrontation to some confrontations - or, if not confrontations, at least disagreements - centered on relatively new themes. of international concerns; clashes - or disagreements that are generating an unfair and, of course, unsafe distancing between the developed, powerful, rich and arbitrating "northern" countries of the world, and the "developing" or underdeveloped countries of the "south" .

East-West confrontation allows for the relaxation of international relations previously conditioned by strict security standards, the dominant powers should not be expected to behave contrary to their larger interests, transgressed in morals and justice by the power capable of guaranteeing them.

It is to be expected that, liberated from the limits imposed by the balance of the two superpowers of the global confrontation, the great powers will practice less flexible conduct within the "north x south" "west x east" complex in what they believe to be critical matters to themselves or to the world.

This is a still very uncertain and unpredictable scenario, which cannot be unaware of the military issue. In the predictable future (ten to twenty years) serious political-strategic issues involving the largest powers of the world in opposite fields are unlikely to occur in the world.

However, this scenario of global peace does not prevent the occurrence of localized and minor conflicts, for which the deterrence of the nuclear power of the powerful is innocuous.

Indeed, one cannot dismiss as completely unlikely the singular cases of "irrationality" and others, not so unlikely, of misconceptions of all kinds in the less developed world, full of inflammable situations born in decades, centuries and even millennia of divergences (the The Middle East crisis was not created by the policies of recent Arab, Israeli and Iranian leaders, which only continue five thousand years of turbulent history), social and economic needs, demographic problems and territorial disputes.

All of these disturbing factors, which hinder the smooth and routine practice of human rights and citizenship, are natural causes of the lack of appetite for, or fragility of, democracy that, when it exists, is often overwhelmed.

On the other hand, in a process of regenerative cause and effect, its absence or fragility complicates conciliation capable of preventing aggravation of antagonisms.

Cases of irrationality, such as the disagreements of the less developed, must be controlled by military power mounted on US military and high technology.

In this regard, Chancellor H. Kohl's attention to amending his country's constitution to allow the use of German forces outside NATO space, the establishment of a Franco-German military force to act in favour of the order in which they are concerned, is symptomatic is convenient and the endorsement of the Japanese Congress for the eventual use of force outside the territory of Japan and its surroundings.

This war scheme obviously has nothing to do with wars involving huge armies of citizens and all or nearly all nations, whose first example in the modern world can be detected in the wars of support of the French Revolution and the last in World War II.

In fact, it practically resurrects the pre-1789 scheme of wars waged by relatively small armies.

In fact, it virtually resurrects the pre-1789 scheme of wars waged by relatively small, professional, and sometimes mercenary armies for normally limited purposes.

At first glance, the scheme at hand is sympathetic and seductive because it reduces the breadth of the virtual war universe.

However, a closer analysis suggests doubts: the regulatory action of the order will respond to the principles of justice or to the interests of the powerful not necessarily coincident?

To the extent that interests prevail over principles. How will it be judged what is right or wrong in a serious regional or internal disagreement and by what parameters will the "irrationality" of a given national policy be assessed?

What conviction can one have that the great powers will work for the just order when disorder is not in their immediate vicinity or affecting their vital interests?

In this control scheme guarded by the great powers, what room is there for the old collective defense systems agreed upon in treaties?

Clarifying doubts with a few conspicuous examples:

- Would the occupation (with annexation) of Kuwait deserve such a strong American and European reaction if the oil of the unstable and troubled Middle East was involved?
- Would the ouster of the president of Haiti, where the practice of democracy has never been strong, deserve great attention from the United States had not Haiti been near Cuba and the Caribbean periphery?
- Why the Indonesian disrespect for human rights in Timor (November 1991), with its many dozen dead?
- The two UN-authorized military interventions, the reaction to North Korea's attack on South Korea in 1950 and the liberation of Kuwait in 1991 stemmed primarily from the US political vision and, in the second case, also from that of its developed world allies Middle East oil customers.

In short: dispensing with the cooperation of hypocrisy of the problem, the influence of an essentially ethical order is generally not decisive.

References:

- Acs Zoltan, Audretsch David. *Innovation and Small Firms*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 1990.
- Aerts Kris, Czarnitzki Dirk. *Using Innovation Survey Data to Evaluate R&D Policy: The Case of Flanders*. Catholic University of Leuven, Department of Applied Economics and Steunpunt O&O Statistieken; 2005.
- Aerts Kris, Czarnitzki Dirk. *The Impact of Public R&D Funding in Flanders*. IWT Studies. 2006;54
- Aghion Phillipe, Burgess Robin, Redding Stephen, Zilibotti Fabrizio. *The Unequal Effects of Liberalization: Theory and Evidence from India*. Washington, DC: Center for Economic Policy Research; 2003.
- Agrawal A, Henderson R. *Putting Patents in Context: Exploring Knowledge Transfer from MIT*. *Management Science*. 2002;48(1):44–60.
- Ahluwalia Montek Singh. *State Level Reforms Under Economic Reforms in India*. Stanford University Working Paper No. 96. Mar, 2001.
- Aizcorbe A, Flamm K, Kurshid A. *The Role of Semiconductor Inputs in IT Hardware Price Decline: Computers vs. Communications*, Federal Reserve Finance and Economics Discussion Paper 2002–37. Washington, DC: The Federal Reserve Board of Governors; Aug, 2002. revised 2004.
- Aizcorbe A, Oliner S, Sichel D. *Shifting Trends in Semiconductor Prices and the Pace of Technological Progress*. Federal Reserve Board Finance and Economics Discussion Series Working Paper No. 2006–44. Sep, 2006.
- Alic John A, Branscomb Lewis M, Brooks Harvey, Carter Ashton B, Epstein Gerald L. *Beyond Spin-off: Military and Commercial Technologies in a Changing World*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press; 1992.
- Allen John. *House continuing resolution would bar NASA from China ties*. Politico. Feb 12, 2011.
- Allen Stuart D, Link Albert N, Rosenbaum Dan T. *Entrepreneurship and Human Capital: Evidence of Patenting Activity from the Academic Sector*. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*. 2007;31(6):937–951.

- Allison J, Lemley M. Empirical Evidence on the Validity of Litigated Patents. *AIPLA Quarterly Journal*. 1998;26:185–277.
- Altenburg Tilman, Schmitz Hubert, Stamm Andreas. Breakthrough: China’s and India’s Transition from Production to Innovation. *World Development*. 2008;36(2):325–344.
- Amsden Alice H. *The Rise of “the Rest”: Challenges to the West from Late-industrializing Economies*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 2001.
- Amsden Alice H, Chu Wan-wen. *Beyond Late Development: Taiwan’s Upgrading Policies*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 2003.
- Amsden Alice H, Tschang Ted, Goto Akira. *Do Foreign Companies Conduct R&D in Developing Countries?* Tokyo, Japan: ADB Institute; 2001.
- Aoki Reiko, Nagaoka Sadao. The Consortium Standard and Patent Pools. *The Economic Review (Keizai Kenkyu)*. 2004;55(4):345–356.
- Aoki Reiko, Nagaoka Sadao. Coalition Formation for a Consortium Standard through a Standard Body and a Patent Pool: Theory and Evidence from MPEG2, DVD and 3G. IIR Working Paper WP#05-01. Feb, 2005.
- Applied Research Institute, Inc. *Survey of the Environment for Startups*. Applied Research Institute; Nov, 2006.
- Archibugi Danielle, Howells Jeremy, Michie Jonathan., editors. *Innovation Policy and the Global Economy*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press; 1999.
- Argyres NS, Liebeskind JP. Privatizing the Intellectual Commons: Universities and the Commercialization of Biotechnology. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*. 1998;35:427–454.
- Arora A, Merges RP. Specialized Supply Firms, Property Rights, and Firm Boundaries. *Industrial and Corporate Change*. 2004;13(3):451–476.
- Arora A, Ceccagnoli M, Cohen W. R&D and the Patent Premium. Carnegie-Mellon University and INSEAD: paper presented at the ASSA Annual Meetings; January 2002; Atlanta, Georgia. 2001.
- Arora A, Fosfuri A, Gambardella A. Markets for Technology and Corporate Strategy. In: Granstrand O, editor. *Economics, Law, and Intellectual Property*. Boston, MA: Kluwer Academic Publishers; 2003.
- Arrow KJ. Increasing Returns: Historiographic Issues and Path Dependence. *European Journal of the History of Economic Thought*. 2000;7(2):171–180.
- Arrow Kenneth. *The Rate and Direction of Inventive Activity*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press; 1962. pp. 609–626.
- Arthur W. Competing Technologies, Increasing Returns, and Lock-in by Historical Small Events. *Economic Journal*. 1989;99(2):116–131.
- Asheim Bjorn T, et al., editors. *Regional Innovation Policy for Small-medium Enterprises*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2003.
- Association of University Research Parks. *Worldwide Research & Science Park Directory 1998*. New York: BPI Communications; 1998.
- Association of University Research Parks. *The Power of Place: A National Strategy for Building America’s Communities of Innovation*. Tucson, AZ: Association of University Research Parks; 2008.
- Athreye Suma S. Technology Policy and Innovation: The Role of Competition Between Firms. In: Conceicao Pedro, et al., editors. *Science, Technology, and Innovation Policy: Opportunities and Challenges for the Knowledge Economy*. Westport, CT: Quorum Books; 2000.
- Atkinson Robert. *The Past and Future of America’s Economy-Long Waves of Innovation that Power Cycles of Growth*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2004.
- Atkinson Robert. *Is the Next Economy Taking Shape? Issues in Science and Technology*. Winter. 2006.
- Audretsch DB, editor. *Industrial Policy and Competitive Advantage*. 1 and 2. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 1998.
- Audretsch DB. Agglomeration and the Location of Innovative Activity. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*. 1998;14(2):18–29.
- Audretsch DB, Wessner Charles W., editor. National Research Council. *A Review of the New Initiatives at the NASA Ames Research Center*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2001. *The Prospects for a Technology Park at Ames: A New Economy Model for Industry-Government Partnership?*
- Audretsch DB. *The Entrepreneurial Society*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 2006.

- Audretsch DB, Feldman MP. R&D Spillovers and the Geography of Innovation and Production. *American Economic Review*. 1996;86(3):630–640.
- Audretsch DB, Feldman MP. Innovation in Cities: Science-based Diversity, Specialization, and Localized Competition. *European Economic Review*. 1999;43(2):409–429.
- Audretsch DB, Bozeman B, Combs KL, Feldman MP, Link AN, Siegel DS, Stephan P, Tassej G, Wessner C. The Economics of Science and Technology. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2002;27:155–203.
- Audretsch DB, Grimm H, Wessner CW. *Local Heroes in the Global Village: Globalization and the New Entrepreneurship Policies*. New York: Springer; 2005.
- Auerswald Philip E, Branscomb Lewis M, Demos Nicholas, Min Brian K. NIST GCR 02-841A. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2005. *Understanding Private-Sector Decision Making for Early-Stage Technology Development: A “Between Invention and Innovation Project” Report*.
- Augustine Norman. *Is America Falling Off the Flat Earth?* Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2007.
- Baker Stephen. New York’s Big Hopes for Nano, *BusinessWeek*. Feb 4, 2005.
- Bakouros YL, Mardas DC, Varsakelis NC. Science Parks, a High-Tech Fantasy? An Analysis of the Science Parks of Greece. *Technovation*. 2002;22(2):123–128.
- Baldwin JR, Hanl P, Sabourin D. Determinants of Innovative Activity in Canadian Manufacturing Firms: The Role of Intellectual Property Rights. *Statistics Canada Working Paper No. 122*. Mar, 2000.
- Baldwin John Russel, Hanel Peter. *Innovation and Knowledge Creation in an Open Economy: Canadian Industry and International Implications*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press; 2003.
- Balzat Markus, Pyka Andreas. Mapping National Innovation Systems in the OECD Area. *International Journal of Technology and Globalisation*. 2006;2(1–2):158–176.
- Baptista R. Clusters, Innovation, and Growth: A Survey of the Literature. In: Swann GMP, Prevezer M, Stout D, editors. *The Dynamics of Industrial Clustering*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 1998.
- Bartzokas Anthony, Teubal Morris. The Political Economy of Innovation Policy Implementation in Developing Countries. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*. 2002;11(4–5)
- Battelle. *R&D Magazine*. Dec, 2009.
- Beinhocker Eric D. *Origin of Wealth—Evolution, Complexity, and the Radical Remaking of Economics*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Business School; 2007.
- Bennis Warren, Biederman Patricia Ward. *Organizing Genius*. New York: Basic Books; 1997.
- Berlin Leslie. *The Man Behind the Microchip: Robert Noyce and the Invention of Silicon Valley*. New York: Oxford University Press; 2005.
- Bessen J, Meurer MJ. *The Patent Litigation Explosion*. Research on Innovation and Boston University School of Law: manuscript. Aug, 2005.
- Bhidé Amar. Venturesome Consumption, Innovation and Globalization. Paper presented at the Centre on Capitalism & Society and CESifo Venice Summer Institute 2006, “Perspectives on the Performance of the Continent’s Economies,”; 21–22 July 2006; San Servolo, Italy: Venice International University; 2006.
- Biegelbauer Peter S, Borrás Susana., editors. *Innovation Policies in Europe and the U.S.: The New Agenda*. Aldershot, UK: Ashgate; 2003.
- Birch David. Who Creates Jobs? *The Public Interest*. 1981;65:3–14.
- Blanpied William A. Inventing U.S. Science Policy. *Physics Today*. 1998;51(2):34–40.
- Block Fred, Keller Matthew. Where Do Innovations Come From? Transformations in the U.S. National Innovation System, 1970–2006. *The Information Technology and Innovation Forum*. Jul, 2008.
- Blomström Magnus, Kokko Ari, Sjöholm Fredrik. Growth & Innovation Policies for a Knowledge Economy: Experiences from Finland, Sweden, & Singapore. *EIJS Working Paper, Series No. 156*. 2002
- Bonvillian William B. Power Play, The DARPA Model and U.S. Energy Policy. *The American Interest*. 2006;II(2):39–48.
- Borrás Susana. *The Innovation Policy of the European Union: From Government to Governance*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2003.

- Borrus Michael, Stowsky Jay. Technology Policy and Economic Growth. In: Edquist Charles, McKelvey Maureen., editors. Systems of Innovation: Growth, Competitiveness and Employment. Vol. 2. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2000.
- Bradsher Pete. China-U.S. Trade Dispute Has Broad Implications. New York Times. Sep 14, 2009.
- Branscomb LM, Auerswald PE. Taking Technical Risks: How Innovators, Executives, and Investors Manage High-Tech Risks. Boston, MA: The MIT Press; 2001.
- Branscomb Lewis M, Auerswald Philip E. NIST GCR 02-841. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; Nov, 2002. Between Invention and Innovation: An Analysis of Funding for Early-Stage Technology Development.
- Braudel Fernand. Capitalism and Material Life 1400–1800. London, UK: Harper Colophon Books; 1973.
- Breschi S, Lissoin F. Knowledge Spillovers and Local Innovation Systems: A Critical Survey. Industrial and Corporate Change. 2001;10(4):975–1005.
- Breznitz Dan. Innovation in the State: Political Choice and Strategies for Growth in Israel, Taiwan, and Ireland. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press; 2007.
- Breznitz D, Murphree Run of the Red Queen; Government, Innovation, and Globalization and Economic Growth in China. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press; 2011.
- Broder J, Ansfield J. China and U.S. Seek a Truce on Greenhouse Gases. The New York Times. Jun 7, 2009.
- Browning L, Shetler J. SEMATECH: Saving the U.S. Semiconductor Industry. College Station, TX: Texas A&M University Press; 2000.
- Bush Nathan. Chinese Competition Policy, It Takes More than a Law. China Business Review. 05-06, 2005.
- Bush Vannevar. Science: The Endless Frontier. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office; 1945.
- Capron Henri, Cincera Michele. Strengths and Weaknesses of the Flemish Innovation System: An External Viewpoint. Brussels, Belgium: IWT; 2006.
- Caracostas Paraskevas, Muldur Ugur. The Emergence of the New European Union Research and Innovation Policy. In: Laredo P, Mustar P, editors. Research and Innovation Policies in the New Global Economy: An International Comparative Analysis. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2001.
- Castells M, Hall P. Technopoles of the World. London, UK: Oxford University Press; 1994.
- Cebrowski Arthur, Garska John. Network Centric Warfare: Its Origin and Future; U.S. Naval Institute Proceedings; Jan, 1998.
- Center for Economic Development and Business Research. Kansas Aviation Manufacturing. Wichita State University: W. Frank Barton School of Business; Sep, 2008.
- Chambers John., editor. The Oxford Companion to American Military History. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 1999.
- Chan KF, Lau Theresa. Assessing Technology Incubator Programs in the Science Park: The Good, the Bad and the Ugly. Technovation. 2005;25(10):1215–1228.
- Chand Satish, Sen Kunal. Trade Liberalization and Productivity Growth: Evidence from Indian Manufacturing. Review of Development Economics. 2002 Feb;6
- Chang Connie, Shipp Stephanie, Wang Andrew. The Advanced Technology Program: A Public-Private Partnership for Early-stage Technology Development. Venture Capital. 2002;4(4):363–370.
- Chao Loretta. China Plans to Ease Rules That Irked Companies. The Wall Street Journal. Jul 1, 2011.
- Chesbrough Henry. Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Business School Press; Apr, 2003.
- China Luring ‘Sea Turtles’ Home. China Daily. Dec 18, 2008.
- China Agrees to Delay Software Procurement Rule While Talking with U.S. China Trade Extra. Jul 11, 2005.
- Chinese Ministry of Finance. Opinions of the Ministry of Finance on Implementing Government Procurement Policies That Encourage Indigenous Innovation. Cai Ku [2006]. Jun 13, 2006.
- Chordà IM. Towards the Maturity State: An Insight into the Performance of French Technopoles. Technovation. 1996;16(3):143–152.
- Chu Ng Ying, Li Sung-ko. Efficiency and productivity growth in Chinese universities during the post-reform period. China Economic Review. 2009;20

- Chuma Hiroyuki. Increasing Complexity and Limits of Organization in the Microlithography Industry: Implications for Science-based Industries. *Research Policy*. 2006;35:394–411.
- Chuma Hiroyuki, Hashimoto Norikazu. Moore's Law, Increasing Complexity and Limits of Organization: Modern Significance of Japanese DRAM ERA, NISTEP Discussion Paper No. 44. National Institute of Science and Technology Policy; 2007.
- Cimoli Mario, della Giusta Marina. The Nature of Technological Change and its Main Implications on National and Local Systems of Innovation. IIASA Interim Report IR-98-029. 2000.
- Cincera Michele. Comparison of Regional Approaches to Foster Innovation in the European Union: The Case of Flanders. Brussels, Belgium: IWT; 2006.
- Cincera Michele. R&D Activities of Flemish Companies in the Private Sector: An Analysis for the Period 1998–2002. Brussels, Belgium: IWT; 2006.
- Clark B. Places of Inquiry. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press; 1995.
- Clarke P. LETI, Crolles Alliance Open \$350-million 32-nm Research Fab. *EE Times*. Apr 24, 2004.
- Clarke P, LaPedus M, Santarini M. IBM-led Consortium to Build Fab in N.Y. *EE Times*. Jan 5, 2005.
- Clough G Wayne. The Role of the Research University in Fostering Innovation. The Americas Competitiveness Forum. Jun 12, 2007.
- Coakes Elayne, Smith Peter. Developing Communities of Innovation by Identifying Innovation Champions. *The Learning Organization: An International Journal*. 2007;14(1):74–85.
- Coburn Christopher, Berglund Dan. Partnerships: A Compendium of State and Federal Cooperative Programs. Columbus, OH: Battelle Press; 1995.
- Cohen W. Thoughts and Questions on Science Parks. Presented at the National Science Foundation Science Parks Indicators Workshop; Greensboro: University of North Carolina; 2002.
- Cohen W, Florida R, Goe R. University-Industry Research Centers in the United States. Pittsburgh, PA: Carnegie-Mellon University; 1992.
- Cohen W, Nelson R, Walsh J. NBER Working Paper 7552. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research; 2000. Protecting Their Intellectual Assets: Appropriability Conditions and Why U.S. Manufacturing Firms Patent (or Not).
- Cohen WM, Goto A, Nagata A, Nelson RR, Walsh JP. R&D Spillovers, Patents and the Incentives to Innovate in Japan and the United States. *Research Policy*. 2002;1425:1–19.
- Combs Kathryn L, Link Albert N. Innovation Policy in Search of an Economic Paradigm: The Case of Research Partnerships in the United States. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*. 2003;15(2)
- Conant Jennet. Tuxedo Park. New York: Simon & Shuster; 2002.
- Conant Jennet. 109 East Palace. New York: Simon & Shuster; 2005.
- Cooper Helene, Lander M. U.S. Shifts Focus to Press China for Market Access. *New York Times*. 2011 Jan 18
- Council on Competitiveness. Innovate America: Thriving in a World of Challenge and Change. Washington, DC: Council on Competitiveness; 2005.
- Council of Economic Advisors. Economic Report to the President. 1995.
- Council on Government Relations. Technology Transfer in U.S. Research Universities: Dispelling Common Myths. Washington, DC: Council on Government Relations; 2000.
- Crafts NFR. The Golden Age of Economic Growth in Western Europe, 1950–1973. *Economic History Review*. 1995;3:429–447.
- Czarnitzki Dirk, O'Byrnes Niall. Innovation and the Impact on Productivity in Flanders. *Tijdschrift voor Economie en Management*. 2007;52(2)
- Dahlman Carl J. India and the Knowledge Economy: Leveraging Strengths and Opportunities. Washington, DC: World Bank Publications; 2005.
- Dahlman Carl J, Aubert Jean Eric. China and the Knowledge Economy: Seizing the 21st Century. Washington, DC: The World Bank; 2001.
- Dahlman Carl, Utz Anuja. India and the Knowledge Economy: Leveraging Strengths and Opportunities. Washington, DC: The World Bank; 2005.
- Daneke Gregory A. Beyond Schumpeter: Non-linear Economics and the Evolution of the U.S. Innovation System. *Journal of Socioeconomics*. 1998;27(1):97–117.

- Darby Michael, Zucker Lynne G, Wang Andrew J. NISTIR 6943. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2002. Program Design and Firm Success in the Advanced Technology Program: Project Structure and Innovation Outcomes.
- Das Gurcharan. The India Model. Foreign Affairs. 2006;85(4)
- Dasgupta P, David P. Toward a New Economics of Science. Research Policy. 1994;23:487–521.
- David PA. Clio and the Economics of QWERTY. American Economic Review. 1985;75(2):332–337.
- Davidsson Per. Methodological Concerns in the Estimation of Job Creation in Different Firm Size Classes, Working Paper. Jönköping International Business School; 1996.
- Davis Steven, Haltiwanger John, Schuh Scott. Small Business and Job Creation: Dissecting the Myth and Reassessing the Facts, Working Paper No. 4492. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research; 1993.
- Debackere Koenraad, Veugelers Reinhilde. The Role of Academic Technology Transfer Organizations in Improving Industry Science Links. Research Policy. 2005;34(3):321–342.
- Debackere Koenraad, Glänzel Wolfgang. Using a Bibliometric Approach to Support Research Policy Making: The Case of the Flemish BOF-key. Scientometrics. 2004;59(2)
- Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency. DARPA Over The Years. Arlington, VA: Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency; Oct 27, 2003.
- Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency. DARPA—Bridging the Gap, Powered by Ideas. Arlington, VA: Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency; Feb, 2005.
- de Jonquieres Guy. China and India Cannot Fill the World’s Skills Gap. Financial Times. Jul 12, 2004.
- de Jonquieres Guy. To Innovate, China Needs More than Standards. Financial Times. Jul 12, 2004.
- de Jonquieres Guy. China’s Curious Marriage of Convenience. Financial Times. Jul 19, 2006.
- De la Mothe J, Paquet Gilles. National Innovation Systems, ‘Real Economies’ and Instituted Processes. Small Business Economics. 1998;11:101–111.
- Deng Xiaoping. Address at the First National Science Congress. 1978. General Secretary of the Communist Party of China Central Committee.
- U.S.-China Clean Energy Cooperation: A Progress Report by the U.S. Department of Energy. Department of Energy; Jan, 2011.
- De Proft A. Presentation at National Academies symposium on “Synergies in Regional and National Policies in the Global Economy.”; Leuven, Belgium. Sep, 2006.
- Dirks S, Keeling M. Executive Report. “A Vision of Smarter Cities: How Cities Can Lead the Way into a Prosperous and Sustainable Future,” IBM Global Business Services. 2009
- Doloreux David. Regional Innovation Systems in Canada: A Comparative Study. Regional Studies. 2004;38(5):479–492.
- Dries Ilse, van Humbeek Peer, Larosse Jan. Linking Innovation Policy and Sustainable Development in Flanders. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2005.
- Dudas J. Statement of the Honorable Jon W. Dudas Deputy Under Secretary of Commerce for Intellectual Property and Director of the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office before the Subcommittee on Intellectual Property, Committee on the Judiciary. U.S. Senate; 2005. <http://judiciary.senate.gov>.
- Eaton Jonathan, Gutierrez Eva, Kortum Samuel. “European Technology Policy” NBER Working Papers 6827. Dec 17, 1998.
- “Competing Through Innovation” The Economist. 2005.
- Edler J, Kuhlmann S. Towards One System? The European Research Area Initiative, the Integration of Research Systems and the Changing Leeway of National Policies. Technikfolgenabschätzung: Theorie und Praxis. 2005;1(4):59–68.
- Chinese Province Pays to Get 300-mm Wafer Fab. EE Times. Jun 28, 2006.
- Ehlen Mark A. Economic Impacts of Flow-Control Machining Technologies: Early Applications in the Automobile Industry. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 1999. NISTIR 6373.
- Ehlers Vernon J. Unlocking Our Future: Toward a New National Science Policy, A Report to Congress by the House Committee on Science. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office; 1998.
- Ehrenberg R. Tuition Rising. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press; 2000.

- Eickelpasch Alexander, Fritsch Michael. Contests for Cooperation: A New Approach in German Innovation Policy. *Research Policy*. 2005;34:1269–1282.
- SMIC Gets \$3B Nod from Chain's Wuhan Government. *Electronic News*. May 22, 2006.
- Endquist Charles., editor. *Systems of Innovation: Technologies, Institutions, and Organizations*. London, UK: Pinter; 1997.
- Tables 8–12, State Energy Consumption Estimates: 1960 through 2007. Energy Information Administration; 2009.
- Engardio Pete. Can the Future be Built in America? Inside the U.S. Manufacturing Crisis. *Business Week*. Sep 21, 2009.
- EOS Gallup Europe. *Entrepreneurship, Flash Eurobarometer 146*. Jan, 2004. Accessed at <http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/enterprise_policy/survey/eurobarometer146en.pdf>.
- European Commission. *Innovation in Candidate Countries: Strengthening Industrial Performance*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities; May, 2003.
- European Commission. *Investing in Research: An Action Plan for Europe 2003*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities; 2003.
- European Commission. *3rd S&T Indicators Report*. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Communities; 2003.
- Evans D, Jovanovic B. An Estimated Model of Entrepreneurial Choice under Liquidity Constraints. *Journal of Political Economy*. 1989;97:808–827.
- Evans Harold. *They Made America*, Sloan Foundation Project. New York: Little, Brown and Company; 2005.
- Executive Office of the President. *A Strategy for American Innovation: Driving Towards Sustainable Growth and Quality Jobs*. 2009. http://www.whitehouse.gov/assets/documents/SEPT_20_Innovation_Whitepaper_FINAL.pdf>.
- Faems Dries, Van Looy Bart, Debackere Koenraad. Interorganizational Collaboration and Innovation: Toward a Portfolio Approach. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*. 2005;22(3):238–250.
- Fan W, White MJ. NBER Working Paper, Series 9340. Boston, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research; 2002. Personal Bankruptcy and the Level of Entrepreneurial Activity.
- Fangerberg Jan. *Technology, Growth, and Competitiveness: Selected Essays*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2002.
- Federal Communications Commission. *Connecting America: The National Broadband Plan*. Washington, DC: Federal Communications Commission; 2009.
- 2004 WTO Dispute Settlement Proceeding Regarding China: Value Added Tax on Integrated Circuits. *Federal Register Notice*. Apr 21, 2004.
- Federal Trade Commission. *To Promote Innovation: The Proper Balance of Patent and Competition Law Policy*. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office; Oct, 2003.
- Feigenbaum Evan. *China's Techno-Warriors: National Security and Strategic Competition from the Nuclear to the Information Age*. Stanford: Stanford University Press; 2003.
- Feldman Maryann, Link Albert N. *Innovation Policy in the Knowledge-based Economy, Economics of Science, Technology and Innovation*. Vol. 23. Boston, MA: Kluwer Academic Press; 2001.
- Feldman Maryann P, Link Albert N, Siegel Donald S. *The Economics of Science and Technology: An Overview of Initiatives to Foster Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Economic Growth*. Boston, MA: Kluwer Academic Press; 2002.
- Feldman Maryann, Feller Irwin, Bercovitz Janet, Burton Richard. *Equity and the Technology Transfer Strategies of American Research Universities*. *Management Science*. 2002;48(1):105–121.
- Feller Irwin. *Technology Transfer from Universities*. In: Smart John., editor. *Higher Education: Handbook of Theory and Research*. XII. New York: Agathon Press; 1997.
- Feller Irwin. *A Comparative Analysis of the Processes and Organizational Strategies Engaged in by Research Universities Participating in Industry-University Research Relationships*. Final report submitted to the University of California Industry-University Cooperative Research Program, Agreement No. M-447646-19927-3. 2004.
- Ferguson R, Olofsson C. Science Parks and the Development of NTBFs: Location, Survival and Growth. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2004;29(1):5–17.
- Field AJ. The Most Technologically Progressive Decade of the Century. *American Economic Review*. Sep, 2003. p. 1406.

- World Leader in Patents Focuses on Incremental Innovations. *The Financial Times*. Oct 12, 2005.
- Flamm K. *Mismanaged Trade: Strategic Policy and the Semiconductor Industry*. Washington, DC: The Brookings Institution; 1996.
- Flamm K. *Microelectronics Innovation: Understanding Moore's Law and Semiconductor Price Trends*. *International Journal of Technology, Policy, and Management*. 2003;3(2)
- Flamm K. *The New Economy in Historical Perspective: Evolution of Digital Technology*, *New Economy Handbook*. St. Louis, MO: Academic Press; 2003.
- Flamm K. National Research Council. *SEMATECH Revisited: Assessing Consortium Impacts on Semiconductor Industry R&D*. In: Wessner Charles W., editor. *Securing the Future: Regional and National Programs to Support the Semiconductor Industry*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2003.
- Florida Richard, Gulden Tim, Mellander Charlotta. *The Rise of the Mega-Region*. Oct, 2007.
- Foerst Ann. *God in the Machine*. New York: Penguin Books; 2005.
- Fonfria Antonio, Diaz de la Guardia Carlos, Alvarez Isabel. *The Role of Technology and Competitiveness Policies: A Technology Gap Approach*. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Economics*. 2002;13(1-2-3):223–241.
- Fong Glenn R. *Follower at the Frontier: International Competition and Japanese Industrial Policy*. *International Studies Quarterly*. 1998;42(2)
- Fong Glenn R. *ARPA Does Windows: The Defense Underpinning of the PC Revolution*. *Business and Politics*. 2001;3(3)
- Foray Dominique, Llerena Patrick. *Information Structure and Coordination in Technology Policy: A Theoretical Model and Two Case Studies*. *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*. 1996;6(2)
- Friedman Thomas. *The World Is Flat: A Brief History of the 21st Century*. New York: W. H. Freeman; 2005.
- Fukugawa N. *Science Parks in Japan and Their Value-Added Contributions to New Technology-based Firms*. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*. 2006;24(2):381–400.
- Furman Jeffrey L, Porter Michael E, Stern Scott. *The Determinants of National Innovative Capacity*. *Research Policy*. 2002;31:899–933.
- Gallaher MP, Link AN, Petrusa JE. *Innovation in the U.S. Service Sector*. London, UK: Routledge; 2006.
- Geiger R. *To Advance Knowledge*. New York: Oxford University Press; 1986.
- Geiger R. *Research and Relevant Knowledge*. New York: Oxford University Press; 1993.
- Geithner Timothy. *Joint Press Availability in Beijing*. China: May 25, 2010.
- George Gerard, Prabhu Ganesh N. *Developmental Financial Institutions as Technology Policy Instruments: Implications for Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*. *Research Policy*. 2003;32(1):89–108.
- Gibb MJ. *Science Parks and Innovation Centres: Their Economic and Social Impact*. Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier; 1985.
- Goldstein HA, Luger MI. *Science/Technology Parks and Regional Development Theory*. *Economic Development Quarterly*. 1990;4(1):64–78.
- Goldstein HA, Luger MI. *University-based Research Parks as a Rural Development Strategy*. *Policy Studies Journal*. 1992;20(2):249–263.
- Goodwin James C, et al. *Technology Transition*. Arlington, VA: Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency; 1999.
- Government of the People's Republic of China. *Anticompetitive Practices of Multinational Companies and Countermeasures*. Administration of Industry and Commerce, Office of Antimonopoly, Fair Trade Bureau, State Administration of Industry and Commerce; May, 2004.
- Government of the People's Republic of China. *Article 10: Exemptions of Monopoly Agreements*. *Anti-Monopoly Law of the People's Republic of China*. 2005. Revised July 27.
- Government of the People's Republic of China, Ministry of Information Industry. *Outline of the 11th Five-Year Plan and Medium-and- Long-Term Plan for 2020 for Science and Technology Development in the Information Industry*, *Xin Bu Ke*. Aug 29, 2006.
- Government of the People's Republic of China, National Development and Reform Commission. *The 11th Five-Year Plan*. Mar 19, 2006. < http://english.gov.cn/2006-07/26/content_346731.htm>.
- Grande Edgar. *The Erosion of State Capacity and European Innovation Policy: A Comparison of German and EU Information Technology Policies*. *Research Policy*. 2001;30(6):905–921.

- Grayson L. *Science Parks: An Experiment in High-Technology Transfer*. London, UK: The British Library Board; 1993.
- Griffing Bruce. *Between Invention and Innovation, Mapping the Funding for Early-Stage Technologies*. Presentation at Carnegie Conference Center; Washington, DC. January 25. 2001.
- Griliches Z. The Search for R&D Spillovers. *Scandinavian Journal of Economics*. 1993;94(S):S29–S47.
- Grindley Peter, Mowery David, Silverman Brian. SEMATECH and Collaborative Research: Lessons in the Design of High Technology Consortia. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*. 1994;13(4):723–758.
- Grove A. *Swimming Across*. New York: Warner Books; 2001.
- Gu Shulin, Bengt-Åke Lundvall. Policy learning as a key process in the transformation of the Chinese Innovation Systems, *Asian Innovation Systems in Transition*. Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd; 2006.
- Guo Ban Han No. 30. Letter from the General Office of the State Council on Approving the Formulation of the Rules for Implementation of the Several Supporting Policies for Implementation of the Outline of the National Medium and Long-term Plan for Development of Science and Technology. *Gazette of the State Council*. Jun 20, 2006.
- Guy I. A Look at Aston Science Park. *Technovation*. 1996;16(5):217–218.
- Guy I. New Ventures on an Ancient Campus. *Technovation*. 1996;16(6):269–270.
- Hackett SM, Dilts DM. A Systematic Review of Business Incubation Research. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2004;29(1):55–82.
- Hall BH. The Assessment: Technology Policy. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*. 2002;18(1):1–9.
- Hall BH. Exploring the Patent Explosion. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2005;30:35–48.
- Hall BH, Link AN, Scott JT. Barriers Inhibiting Industry from Partnering with Universities: Evidence from the Advanced Technology Program. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2001;26(1–2):87–98.
- Hall BH, Link AN, Scott JT. Universities as Research Partners. *Review of Economics and Statistics*. 2003;85(2):485–491.
- Hall BH, Jaffe A, Trajtenberg M. Market Value and Patent Citations. *RAND Journal of Economics*. 2005;36:16–38.
- Hall BH, Ziedonis RH. The Patent Paradox Revisited: An Empirical Study of Patenting in the U.S. Semiconductor Industry. 1979–1995. *RAND Journal of Economics*. 2001;32:101–128.
- Halpern Mark. The Trouble with the Turing Test. *The New Atlantis*. 2006 Winter;11:42–63.
- Hane G. Comparing University-Industry Linkages in the United States and Japan. In: Branscomb L, Kodama F, Florida R, editors. *Industrializing Knowledge*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 1999.
- Hansson F, Husted K, Vestergaard J. Second Generation Science Parks: From Structural Holes Jockeys to Social Capital Catalysts of the Knowledge Society. *Technovation*. 2005;25(9):1039–1049.
- Hart David. *Forged Consensus*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press; 1998.
- Hashimoto T. The Hesitant Relationship Reconsidered: University-Industry Cooperation in Postwar Japan. In: Branscomb Lewis M, Kodama Fumio, Florida Richard., editors. *Industrializing Knowledge. University-Industry Linkage in Japan and the United States*; Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 1999.
- Hassan Mohamed HA. Small Things and Big Changes in the Developing World. *Science*. 2005 Jul 1;309:65–66. [[PubMed](#)]
- Hayashi Fumio, Prescott Edward C. The 1990s in Japan: A Lost Decade. *Review of Economic Dynamics*. 2002;5(1):206–235.
- Heller M, Eisenberg R. Can Patents Deter Innovation? The Anticommons in Biomedical Research. *Science*. 1998;280:698. [[PubMed](#)]
- Henderson JV. The Efficiency of Resource Usage and City Size. *Journal of Urban Economics*. 1986;19(1):47–70.
- Henderson Jennifer A, Smith John J. *Academia, Industry, and the Bayh-Dole Act: An Implied Duty to Commercialize, White Paper*. Center for the Integration of Medicine and Innovative Technology. Harvard University; Oct, 2002.
- Henderson R, Orsenigo L, Pisano GP. The Pharmaceutical Industry and the Revolution in Molecular Biology: Interactions among Scientific, Institutional, and Organizational Change. In:

- Mowery DC, Nelson RR, editors. *Sources of Industrial Leadership*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press; 1999.
- Henderson R, Trajtenberg M, Jaffe A. Universities as a Source of Commercial Technology: A Detailed Analysis of University Patenting, 1965–1988. *Review of Economics and Statistics*. 1998;80(1):119–127.
 - Hennessy JL, Patterson DA. *Computer Architecture: A Quantitative Approach*. 3. San Francisco, CA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc; 2002.
 - Hicks D, Breitzman T, Olivastro D, Hamilton K. The Changing Composition of Innovative Activity in the U.S.—A Portrait Based on Patent Analysis. *Research Policy*. 2001;30(4):681–704.
 - Hilpert U, Ruffieux B. Innovation, Politics and Regional Development: Technology Parks and Regional Participation in High-Technology in France and West Germany. In: Hilpert U, editor. *Regional Innovation and Decentralization: High-Technology Industry and Government Policy*. London, UK: Routledge; 1991.
 - Himmelberg C, Petersen BC. R&D and Internal Finance: A Panel Study of Small Firms in High-Tech Industries. *Review of Economics and Statistics*. 1994;76(1):38–51.
 - Holtz-Eakin D, Joulfian D, Rosen H. Striking it Out: Entrepreneurial Survival and Liquidity Constraints. *Journal of Political Economy*. 1994;102(1):53–75.
 - Hoshi Takeo, Kashyap Anil. Japan's Economic and Financial Crisis: An Overview. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*. 2004 Winter.
 - Howell Thomas. National Research Council. *Competing Programs: Government Support for Microelectronics*. In: Wessner Charles W., editor. *Securing the Future: Regional and National Programs to Support the Semiconductor Industry*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2003.
 - Howell Thomas, et al. *China's Emerging Semiconductor Industry*. San Jose, CA: Semiconductor Industry Association; Oct, 2003.
 - Hu Jintao. Keynote Speech. Nov 27, 2005. General Secretary of the Communist Party of China Central Committee.
 - Hu Jintao. Speech to the Seventeenth Communist Party of China National Conference. Oct, 2007. General Secretary of the Communist Party of China Central Committee.
 - Hu Jintao. Speech to United Nations General Assembly. Sep 22, 2009. President of China.
 - Hu Zhijian. IPR Policies In China: Challenges and Directions. Presentation at Industrial Innovation in China. Levin Institute Conference; July 24–26. 2006.
 - Huang Can, Amorim C, Spinoglio M, Gouveia B, Medina A. Organization, Programme and Structure: An Analysis of the Chinese Innovation Policy Framework. *R&D Management*. 2004;34(4)
 - Huang Yasheng, Khanna Tarun. Can India Overtake China? *Foreign Policy*. 2003 07-08
 - Huddleson Lillian, Daitch Vicki. *True Genius—The Life and Science of John Bardeen*. Washington, DC: Joseph Henry Press; 2002.
 - Hughes Kent. *Building the Next American Century: The Past and Future of American Economic Competitiveness*. 14. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson Center Press; 2005.
 - Hughes Kent H. Facing the Global Competitiveness Challenge. *Issues in Science and Technology*. 2005;XXI(4):72–78.
 - Hulsink W, Bouwman H, Elfring T. Silicon Valley in the Polder? Entrepreneurial Dynamics, Virtuous Clusters and Vicious Firms in the Netherlands and Flanders. *ERIM Report Series Research in Management (ERS-2007-048-ORG)*. 2007
 - Hundley Richard O. *Past Revolutions, Future Transformations: What Can the History of Revolutions in Military Affairs Tell Us About Transforming the U.S. Military*. Rand Corporation, National Research Institute; 1999.
 - Iansati Marco, Levien Roy. *The Keystone Advantage*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Business School Press; 2005.
 - Industrial Research Institute, Inc. *Industry-University Intellectual Property*, Position Paper. External Research Directors Network; Apr, 2001.
 - Inkpen Andrew C, Pien Wang. An Examination of Collaboration and Knowledge Transfer: China-Singapore Suzhou Industrial Park. *Journal of Management Studies*. 2006;43(4):779–811.
 - Industry Worried China Backing out of Commitment to Join GPA. *Inside U.S.-China Trade*. Sep 27, 2006.

- Institute for International Education. International Student Enrollments Rose Modestly in 2009/10, Led by Strong Increase in Students from China, Press Release. 2011. <<http://www.iie.org/en>>.
- International Association of Science Parks (IASP). 2000. <<http://www.iaspworld.org/information/definitions.php>>.
- International Telecommunications Union. ITU Internet Reports 2005: The Internet of Things. 2005. <http://www.itu.int/osg/spu/publications/internetofthings/InternetofThings_summary.pdf>.
- Jacobs Tom. Biotech Follows Dot.com Boom and Bust. *Nature*. 2002;20(10):973.
- Jaffe AB. Real Effects of Academic Research. *American Economic Review*. 1989;79(5):957–970.
- Jaffe AB. NIST GCR 97–708. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 1997. Economic Analysis of Research Spillovers: Implications for the Advanced Technology Program.
- Jaffe AB. The Importance of ‘Spillovers’ in the Policy Mission of the ATP. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 1998;23(1):11–19.
- Jaffe AB. The U.S. Patent System in Transition: Policy Innovation and the Innovation Process. *Research Policy*. 2000;29:531–557.
- Jaffe AB, Lerner J. *Innovation and Its Discontents: How Our Broken Patent System Is Endangering Innovation and Progress, and What to Do About It*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press; 2006.
- Jaffe AB, Lerner J, Stern S, editors. *Innovation Policy and the Economy*. Vol. 3. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 2003.
- Jaffe AB, Trajtenberg M, Henderson R. Geographic Localization of Knowledge Spillovers as Evidenced by Patent Citations. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*. 1993;108(3):577–598.
- Japan Patent Office. Reports on Technology Trend and Patent Application: Life Science (in Japanese). 2003.
- Jasanoff Sheila., editor. *Comparative Science and Technology Policy*. Elgar Reference Collection, International Library of Comparative Public Policy. Vol. 5. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 1997.
- Jorgenson DW. Information Technology and the U.S. Economy. *American Economic Review*. 2001 Mar;91(1)
- Jorgenson DW. U.S. Economic Growth in the Information Age. *Issues in Science and Technology*. 2001 Fall.
- Jorgenson DW, Stiroh Kevin. Raising the Speed Limit: Economic Growth in the Information Age. In: Jorgenson Dale, Wessner Charles., editors. *Measuring and Sustaining the New Economy*. National Research Council; Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2002.
- Jorgenson DW, Motohashi K. The Role of Information Technology in the Economy: Comparison between Japan and the United States, Prepared for RIETI/KEIO Conference on Japanese Economy: Leading East Asia in the 21st Century? Keio University; May 30, 2003.
- Joy William. Why the Future Does Not Need Us. *Wired*. Apr, 2000.
- Kaelble Steve. Good Neighbors: Indiana’s Certified-Technology-park Program. *Indiana Business Magazine*. Jul 1, 2004.
- Kapur Devesh. The Kauffman Foundation and the Information Technology and Innovation Foundation; Indian Diaspora as a Strategic Asset, *Economic and Political Weekly*. 2003;2007;38(5):445–448. The 2007 State New Economy Index. <<http://www.kauffman.org/items.cfm?itemID=766>>.
- Kawamoto Takuji. What Do the Purified Solow Residuals Tell Us about Japan’s Lost Decade? Bank of Japan IMES Discussion Paper Series. No. 2004-E-5. Tokyo, Japan: Bank of Japan; 2004.
- Kenney Martin., editor. *Understanding Silicon Valley: The Anatomy of an Entrepreneurial Region*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press; 2000.
- Kim Linsu. Imitation to Innovation; The Dynamics of Korea’s Technological Learning. Boston: Harvard Business School Press; 1997. pp. 192–213, pp. 234–243.
- Kim Yong-June. A Korean Perspective on China’s Innovation System. Presentation at Industrial Innovation in China. Levin Institute Conference; July 24–26. 2006.
- Kneller R. University-Industry Cooperation and Technology Transfer in Japan Compared with the U.S.: Another Reason for Japan’s Economic Malaise? *Journal of International Economic Law*. 2003;24:329–450.

- Koizumi Kei. AAAS Publication Number 07-1A. Washington, DC: American Association for the Advancement of Science; 2007. Historical Trends in Federal R&D, AAAS Report XXXII: Research and Development FY2008.
- Kondo Masayuki. Chinese Model to Create High-Tech Start-Ups from Universities and Research Institutes. In: von Zedtwitz M, Haour G, Khalil T, Lefebvre L, editors. Management of Technology: Growth through Business, Innovation and Entrepreneurship. Oxford, UK: Pergamon Press; 2003.
- Kondo Masayuki. Policy Innovation in Science and Technology in Japan—from S&T Policy to Innovation Policy (In Japanese.). Journal of Science Policy and Research Management. 2004;19(3/4):132–140.
- Kondo Masayuki. University spin-offs in Japan. Asian and Pacific Centre for Transfer of Technology, ESCAP, UN; Asia Pacific Tech Monitor. 2004 03-04:37–43.
- Kondo Masayuki. Spin-offs from Public Research Institutes as Domestic Technology Transfer Means—The Case of RIKEN and Riken Industrial Group (In Japanese.). Development Engineering. 2005;11:31–41.
- Kondo Masayuki. University-Industry Partnerships in Japan; Presentation at the conference, 21st Century Innovation Systems for the United States and Japan: Lessons from a Decade of Change; Tokyo, Japan. The National Academies, NISTEP of Japan, and The Institute of Innovation Research of Hitotsubashi University; 2006. <<http://www.nistep.go.jp/IC/ic060110/pdf/5-2.pdf>>.
- Kortum S, Lerner J. What is Behind the Recent Surge in Patenting? Research Policy. 1999;28:1–22.
- Koschatzky Knut. The Regionalization of Innovation Policy: New Options for Regional Change? In: Fuchs G, Shapira Phil, editors. Rethinking Regional Innovation: Path Dependency or Regional Breakthrough? London, UK: Kluwer; 2003.
- Krugman Paul. Geography and Trade. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press; 1991.
- Krugman Paul. Competitiveness: A Dangerous Obsession. Foreign Affairs. 1994 03/04
- Kuhlmann Stephan, Edler Jakob. Scenarios of Technology and Innovation Policies in Europe: Investigating Future Governance—Group of 3. Technological Forecasting & Social Change. 2003;70
- Kumar Deepak. Science and the Raj: 1857–1905. New York: Oxford University Press; 1995.
- Lall Sanjaya. Linking FDI and Technology Development for Capacity Building and Strategic Competitiveness. Transnational Corporations. 2002;11(3):39–88.
- Lanjouw JO, Cockburn I. Do Patents Matter? Empirical Evidence after GATT. NBER Working Paper No. 7495. 2000.
- Lanjouw JO, Lerner J. The Enforcement of Intellectual Property Rights: A Survey of the Empirical Literature. NBER Working Paper No. W6296. 1997. Available at <<http://ssrn.com/abstract=226053>>.
- Laredo Philippe, Mustar Philippe., editors. Research and Innovation Policies in the New Global Economy: An International Perspective. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2001.
- Larosse J. Towards a ‘Third Generation’ Innovation Policy in Flanders: Policy Profile of the Flemish Innovation. Brussels, Belgium: IWT; 2004.
- Lazowska Edward D, Paterson David. An Endless Frontier Postponed. Science. 2005 May 6;308(5723):757. [[PubMed](#)]
- Lebra Takie Sugiyama. The Social Mechanism of Guilt and Shame: The Japanese Case. Anthropological Quarterly. 1971;44(4):241–255.
- Lembke Johan. Competition for Technological Leadership: EU Policy for High Technology. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2002.
- Lemola Tarmo. Convergence of National Science and Technology Policies: The Case of Finland. Research Policy. 2002;31(8–9):1481–1490.
- Lerner J. Patenting in the Shadow of Competitors. Journal of Law and Economics. 1995 Oct;38:463–495.
- Lerner J. Public Venture Capital. In: Wessner Charles W., editor. The Small Business Innovation Program: Challenges and Opportunities. National Research Council; Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1999.
- Lerner J. Patent Policy Shifts and Innovation Over 150 Years. American Economic Review P&P. 2002 May
- Lerner J, Tirole J. Efficiency of Patent Pools. American Economic Review. 2004;94(3):691–711.
- Leslie Stuart, Kargon Robert. Exporting MIT. Osiris. 2006;21:110–130.

- Levin RC, Klevorick AK, Nelson RR, Winter SG. Appropriating the Returns to Industrial R&D. *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*. 1987:783–820.
- Levitt Rachele., editor. *The University/Real Estate Connection: Research Parks and Other Ventures*. Washington, DC: Urban Land Institute; 1987.
- Lewis James A. *Waiting for Sputnik: Basic Research and Strategic Competition*. Washington, DC: Center for Strategic and International Studies; 2005.
- Leyden DP, Link AN, Siegel DS. A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis of the Decision to Locate on a University Research Park. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*. 2008;55(1):23–28.
- Li Jianjun. *The Development and Opening of Tianjin Binhai: New Area & China's Biotechnical Innovations*. Presentation at Industrial Innovation in China; Levin Institute Conference. July 24–26. 2006.
- Licklider JCR. *Man-Computer Symbiosis*. *IRE Transactions on Human Factors in Electronics*. Mar, 1960.
- Lin Otto. Science and Technology Policy and its Influence on the Economic Development of Taiwan. In: Rowen Henry S., editor. *Behind East Asian Growth: The Political and Social Foundations of Prosperity*. New York: Routledge; 1998.
- Lindelöf P, Löfsten H. Science Park Location and New Technology-Based Firms in Sweden: Implications for Strategy and Performance. *Small Business Economics*. 2003;20(3):245–258.
- Lindelöf P, Löfsten H. Proximity as a Resource Base for Competitive Advantage: University-Industry Links for Technology Transfer. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2004;29(3–4):311–326.
- Lindh T, Ohlsson H. Self-Employment and Windfall Gains: Evidence from the Swedish Lottery. *Economic Journal*. 1996;106:1515–1526.
- Link AN. Basic Research and Productivity Increase in Manufacturing: Some Additional Evidence. *American Economic Review*. 1981;71(5):1111–1112.
- Link AN. *Research and Development Activity in U.S. Manufacturing*. New York: Praeger; 1981.
- Link AN. *A Generosity of Spirit: The Early History of the Research Triangle Park*. Research Triangle Park, NC: University of North Carolina Press for the Research Triangle Park Foundation; 1995.
- Link AN. *From Seed to Harvest: The Growth of the Research Triangle Park*. Research Triangle Park, NC: University of North Carolina Press for the Research Triangle Park Foundation; 2002.
- Link AN, Siegel DS. *Technological Change and Economic Performance*. London, UK: Routledge; 2003.
- Link AN, Scott JT. *Public Accountability: Evaluating Technology-Based Institutions*. Norwell, MA: Kluwer Academic Publishers; 1998.
- Link AN, Scott JT. Public/Private Partnerships: Stimulating Competition in a Dynamic Market. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*. 2001;19(5):763–794.
- Link AN, Scott JT. The Growth of Research Triangle Park. *Small Business Economics*. 2003;20(2):167–175.
- Link AN, Scott JT. U.S. Science Parks: The Diffusion of an Innovation and Its Effects on the Academic Mission of Universities. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*. 2003;21(9):1323–1356.
- Link AN, Scott JT. Opening the Ivory Tower's Door: An Analysis of the Determinants of the Formation of U.S. University Spin-Off Companies. *Research Policy*. 2005;34(7):1106–1112.
- Link AN, Scott JT. U.S. University Research Parks. *Journal of Productivity Analysis*. 2006;25(1):43–55.
- Link AN, Scott JT. The Economics of University Research Parks. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*. 2007;23(4):661–674.
- Link AN, Link KR. On the Growth of U.S. Science Parks. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2003;28(1):81–85.
- Litan Robert E, Mitchell Lesa. Should Universities be Agents of Economic Development? *Astra Briefs*. 2008;7:7–8.
- Locke Gary. *Remarks on Clean Energy Trade Mission to China, Indonesia, Briefing at the Washington Foreign Press Center*. May 12, 2010.
- Löfsten Hans, Lindelöf Peter. Science Parks and the Growth of New Technology-based Firms—Academic-industry Links, Innovation and Markets. *Research Policy*. 2002;31(6):859–876.

- Long Guogiang. China's Policies on FDI: Review and Evaluation. In: Moran Theodore H, Graham Edward M, Blomström Magnus., editors. Does Foreign Direct Investment Promote Development? Washington, DC: Institute for International Economics; 2005.
- Luger MI. Introduction: Information Technology and Regional Economic Development. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research & Practice*. 2001
- Luger MI. Smart Places for Smart People: Using Cluster-based Planning in the 21st Century, Creating Enterprise: Igniting Innovation through Business-University-Government Networks. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2007.
- Luger MI, Goldstein HA. *Technology in the Garden*. Chapel Hill, NC: University of North Carolina Press; 1991.
- Luger MI, Goldstein HA. *Research Parks Redux: The Changing Landscape of the Garden*. Washington, DC: U.S. Economic Development Administration; 2006.
- Lundström A, Stevenson L. *Entrepreneurship Policy for the Future*. Stockholm, Sweden: FSF; 2001.
- Lynn Leonard. Collaborative Advantage and China's Evolving Position in the Global Technology System. Presentation at Industrial Innovation in China; Levin Institute Conference. July 24–26, 2006.
- Macher Jeffrey, Mowery David, Hodges David. National Research Council. Semiconductors. In: Mowery David C., editor. *U.S. Industry in 2000: Studies in Competitive Performance*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1999.
- Maddison Angus, Johnston Donald. *The World Economy: A Millennial Perspective*. Paris, France: Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development; 2001.
- Malecki EJ. *Technology and Economic Development*. New York: John Wiley; 1991.
- Mani Sunil. Government, Innovation and Technology Policy: An International Comparative Analysis. *International Journal of Technology and Globalization*. 2004;1(1)
- Mansfield E. Patents and Innovation: An Empirical Study. *Management Science*. 1986;32:173–181.
- Mansfield E. GCR 99–780. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 1996. Estimating Social and Private Returns from Innovations Based on the Advanced Technology Program: Problems and Opportunities.
- Mansfield E. How Fast Does New Industrial Technology Leak Out? *Journal of Industrial Economics*. 1996;34(2):217–224.
- Marshall Andrew. Some Thoughts on Military Revolutions-Second Version, Memorandum for the Record. Aug 23, 1993.
- Mazuzan George. *The National Science Foundation: A Brief History (1950–1985)* NSF 88-16. Arlington, VA: The National Science Foundation; 1988.
- McKibben William. *Enough: Staying Human in an Engineered Age*. New York: Henry Holt & Co; 2003.
- Megginson William L. Towards a Global Model of Venture Capital? *Journal of Applied and Corporate Finance*. 2004;16(1)
- Merges RP. A Comparative Look at Intellectual Property Rights and the Software Industry. In: Mowery David C., editor. *The International Software Industry*. New York: Oxford University Press; 1996.
- Merges RP. As Many as Six Impossible Patents before Breakfast: Property Rights for Business Concepts and Patent System Reform. *Berkeley Technology Law Journal*. 1999
- Merges RP, Nelson RR. On the Complex Economics of Patent Scope. *Columbia Law Review*. 1990;90:839–916.
- Merton RK. The Matthew Effect in Science. *Science*. 1968;159(3810):56–63. [[PubMed](#)]
- METI (Small and Medium Enterprise Agency, Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry). *The 2003 White Paper on Small and Medium Enterprises in Japan*. Tokyo: Japan Small Business Research Institute; 2003.
- METI. *The 2005 White Paper on Small and Medium Enterprises in Japan*. Tokyo: Japan Small Business Research Institute; 2005.
- MEXT. *Annual Report on Science and Technology Promotion Measures 2004: White Paper on Science and Technology, Heisei 16 nendo Kagaku-Gijutu Sinkou-ni-kansuru Nenji-houkoku*. MEXT; 2004.
- Meyer-Krahmer Frieder. The German Innovation System. In: Larédo P, Mustar P, editors. *Research and Innovation Policies in the New Global Economy: An International Comparative Analysis*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2001. pp. 205–252.

- Meyer-Krahmer Frieder. Industrial Innovation and Sustainability—Conflicts and Coherence. In: Archibugi Daniele, Lundvall Bengt-Ake., editors. *The Globalizing Learning Economy*. New York: Oxford University Press; 2001. pp. 177–195.
- Middleton Andrew, Bowns Steven, Hartley Keith, Reid James. The Effect of Defense R&D on Military Equipment Quality. *Defense and Peace Economics*. 2006 Apr;17(2):117–139.
- Miller Roger, Cote Marcel. *Growing the Next Silicon Valley: A Guide for Successful Regional Planning*. Toronto: D. C. Heath and Company; 1987.
- Mills K, Reynolds E, Reamer A. *Clusters and Competitiveness: A New Federal Role for Stimulating Regional Economies*. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution; 2008.
- Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry. *New Economic Growth Strategies 2006*. Tokyo, Japan: Research Institute of Economy, Trade and Industry; 2006. (In Japanese)
- Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare. *Visions of Pharmaceutical Industry in Japan*. 2002. <<http://www.mhlw.go.jp/houdou/2002/04/h0409-1.html>> (In Japanese)
- Mitra Raja. India's Potential as a Global R&D Power. In: Karlsson Magnus., editor. *The Internationalization of Corporate R&D*. Östersund: Swedish Institute for Growth Policy Studies; 2006.
- Miyata Shinpei. *A Free Paradise for Scientists*. (In Japanese.). Bungeishunju; 1983.
- Mody Ashok, Dahlman Carl. Performance and Potential of Information Technology: An International Perspective. *World Development*. 1992;20(12):1703–1719.
- Moore Gordon. National Research Council. *The SEMATECH Contribution*. In: Wessner Charles W., editor. *Securing the Future: Regional and National Programs to Support the Semiconductor Industry*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2003.
- Mooris PR. *A History of The World Semiconductor Industry*. Stevenage, UK: Peter Peregrinus Ltd; 1990.
- Morrison Wayne M. *China-U.S. Trade Issues*. Washington, DC: Congressional Research Service; Jun 1, 2010.
- Morrow Daniel S. Dr. J. Craig Venter-Oral History, Computer World Honors Program. Apr 21, 2003. Available at <<http://cwheroes.org/archives/histories/venter>>.
- Moser P. *How Do Patent Laws Influence Innovation? Evidence from Nineteenth Century World Fairs*. University of California; Berkeley; 2001. working paper.
- Motohashi Kazuyuki. University-industry Collaborations in Japan: The Role of New Technology-based Firms in Transforming the National Innovation System. *Research Policy*. 2005;34:583–594.
- Motohashi Kazuyuki, Yun Xiao. China's Innovation System Reform and Growing Industry and Science Linkages. *Research Policy*. 2007;36:1251–1260.
- Mowery DC, Ziedonis AA. Academic Patent Quality and Quantity Before and After the Bayh-Dole Act in the United States. *Research Policy*. 2002;31(3):399–418.
- Mowery DC, Sampat BN. The Bayh-Dole Act of 1980 and University-Industry Technology Transfer: A Model for Other OECD Governments? *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2005;30(1/2):115–127.
- Mowery DC, Nelson R, Sampat B, Ziedonis A. *The Growth of Patenting and Licensing by U.S. Universities: An Assessment of the Effects of the Bayh-Dole Act of 1980*. *Research Policy*. 2001:30.
- Mowery DC, Nelson R, Sampat B, Ziedonis A. *The Ivory Tower and Industrial Innovation*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press; 2003.
- Muro Mark, Rahman S. *Budget 2011: Industry Clusters as a Paradigm for Job Growth*, Brookings Institution Metropolitan Policy Program. Jun 10, 2010.
- Murphy LM, Edwards PL. *Bridging the Valley of Death: Transitioning from Public to Private Sector Financing*. Golden, CO: National Renewable Energy Laboratory; May, 2003.
- Mustar Phillipe, Laredo Phillipe. Innovation and Research Policy in France (1980–2000) or the Disappearance of the Colbertist State. *Research Policy*. 2002;31:55–72.
- Nadiri I. NBER Working Paper No. 4423. Boston, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research; 1993. *Innovations and Technological Spillovers*.
- Nagaoka Sadao. *How Does Priority Rule Work? Evidence from the Patent Examination Records in Japan*, A Paper Presented for Patent Statistics and Innovation Research Workshop. Research Center for Advanced Science and Technology, University of Tokyo; Nov 25, 2005.
- Nagaoka Sadao. *Reform of Patent System in Japan and Challenges*. Presentation at the conference, “21st Century Innovation Systems for the United States and Japan: Lessons from a Decade of Change”; Tokyo, Japan. The National Academies, NISTEP of Japan, and The Institute

of Innovation Research of Hitotsubashi University; 2006. <<http://www.nistep.go.jp/IC/ic060110/pdf/5-2.pdf>>.

- Nagaoka Sadao. Assessing the R&D Management of Firms by Patent Citation: Evidence from the U.S. Patents. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*. 2007;16(1)
- Nagaoka Sadao, Tsukada Naotoshi, Shimbo Tomoyuki. IIR Working Paper WP#06-08. Institute of Innovation Research, Hitotsubashi University; 2006. The Emergence and Structure of Essential Patents of Standards: Lessons from Three IT Standards.
- Nakamura K, Okada Y, Tohei A. Does the Public Sector Make a Significant Contribution to Biomedical Research in Japan? A Detailed Analysis of Government and University Patenting, 1991–2002, Discussion Paper Series. Competition Policy Research Center. Fair Trade Commission of Japan; 2006. CPDP25-E. <<http://www.jftc.go.jp/cprc/DP/discussionpapers.html>>.
- Nakayama Yasuo, Hosono Mitsuaki, Fukugawa Nobuya, Kondo Masayuki. NISTEP Research Material. No. 119. Tokyo, Japan: National Institute of Science and Technology Policy, Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology; 2005. University-Industry Cooperation: Joint Research and Contract Research. (In Japanese.)
- NASSCOM Research. White Paper, Tracing China's IT Software and Services Industry Evolution. 2007.
- National Academy of Engineering. *The Engineer of 2020: Visions of Engineering in the New Century*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2004.
- National Academy of Sciences/National Academy of Engineering/Insitute of Medicine. *Rising Above the Gathering Storm: Energizing and Employing America for a Brighter Economic Future*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2007.
- National Institute of Science and Technology Policy and Mitsubishi Research Institute. Government S&T Budget Analysis during the First and Second S&T Basic Plans (Dai-ikki oyobi dai-niki Kagaku-Gijutu-Kihonkeikaku kikancho no kenkyuu-kaihatu-soushi no naiyou-bunseki). NISTEP Report No. 84. Mar, 2005.
- National Manufacturing Competitiveness Council. *The National Strategy for Manufacturing*. New Delhi, India: Mar, 2006.
- National Research Council. *Scientific Communication and National Security*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1982.
- National Research Council. *Balancing the National Interest: U.S. National Security Export Controls and Global Economic Competition*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1987.
- National Research Council. *Conflict and Cooperation in National Competition for High-technology Industry*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1996.
- National Research Council. *The Advanced Technology Program: Challenges and Opportunities*. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1999.
- National Research Council. *Funding a Revolution: Government Support for Computing Research*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1999.
- National Research Council. *Industry-Laboratory Partnerships: A Review of the Sandia Science and Technology Park Initiative*. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1999.
- National Research Council. *New Vistas in Transatlantic Science and Technology Cooperation*. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1999.
- National Research Council. *The Small Business Innovation Research Program: Challenges and Opportunities*. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 1999.
- National Research Council. *The Small Business Innovation Research Program: A Review of the Department of Defense Fast Track Initiative*. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2000.
- National Research Council. *U.S. Industry in 2000: Studies in Competitive Performance*. Mowery David C., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2000.
- National Research Council. *The Advanced Technology Program: Assessing Outcomes*. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2001.
- National Research Council. *Building a Workforce for the Information Economy*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2001.
- National Research Council. *Capitalizing on New Needs and New Opportunities: Government-Industry Partnerships in Biotechnology and Information Technologies*. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2001.

- National Research Council. A Review of the New Initiatives at the NASA Ames Research Center. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2001.
- National Research Council. Trends in Federal Support of Research and Graduate Education. Merrill Stephen A., editor. Washington, DC: National Academy Press; 2001.
- National Research Council. Government-Industry Partnerships for the Development of New Technologies: Summary Report. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2003.
- National Research Council. Securing the Future: Regional and National Programs to Support the Semiconductor Industry. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2003.
- National Research Council. A Patent System for the 21st Century. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2004.
- National Research Council. Productivity and Cyclicalities in Semiconductors: Trends, Implications, and Questions. Jorgenson Dale W, Wessner Charles W., editors. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2004.
- National Research Council. The Small Business Innovation Research Program: Program Diversity and Assessment Challenges. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2004. [[PubMed](#)]
- National Research Council. Getting Up to Speed: The Future of Superconducting. Graham Susan L, Snir Marc, Patterson Cynthia A., editors. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2005.
- National Research Council. Policy Implications of International Graduate Students and Post-doctoral Scholars in the United States. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2005.
- National Research Council. Enhancing Productivity Growth in the Information Age: Measuring and Sustaining the New Economy. Jorgenson Dale W, Wessner Charles W., editors. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2007.
- National Research Council. India's Changing Innovation System: Achievements, Challenges, and Opportunities for Cooperation. Wessner Charles W, Shivakumar Sujai J., editors. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2007.
- National Research Council. Innovation Policies for the 21st Century. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2007.
- National Research Council. SBIR and the Phase III Challenge of Commercialization. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2007. [[PubMed](#)]
- National Research Council. An Assessment of the SBIR Program. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2008.
- National Research Council. An Assessment of the SBIR Program at the Department of Energy. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2008.
- National Research Council. An Assessment of the SBIR Program at the National Science Foundation. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2008. [[PubMed](#)]
- National Research Council. Innovative Flanders: Innovation Policies for the 21st Century. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2008.
- National Research Council. 21st Century Innovation Systems for Japan and the United States: Lessons from a Decade of Change. Nagaoka Sadao, Kondo Masayuki, Flamm Kenneth, Wessner Charles., editors. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2009.
- National Research Council. An Assessment of the SBIR Program at the Department of Defense. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2009. [[PubMed](#)]
- National Research Council. An Assessment of the SBIR Program at the National Institutes of Health. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2009.
- National Research Council. An Assessment of the SBIR Program at the National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2009.
- National Research Council. Revisiting the Department of Defense SBIR Fast Track Initiative. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2009.
- National Research Council. Understanding Research, Science, and Technology Parks: Global Best Practices. Wessner Charles W., editor. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2009.

- National Research Council. *The Dragon and the Elephant, Understanding the Development of Innovation Capacity in China and India*. Merrill S, editor. Washington, DC: National Academies Press; 2010.
- National Research Council. *The Future of Photovoltaics Manufacturing in the United States*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2011. Charles W Wessner, Rapporteur.
- National Research Council. *Building the U.S. Battery Industry for Electric-Drive Vehicles: Progress, Challenges, and Opportunities*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; Forthcoming. Charles W Wessner, Rapporteur.
- National Research Council. *Clustering for 21st Century Prosperity*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; Forthcoming. Charles W Wessner, Rapporteur.
- National Research Council. *Growing Innovation Clusters for American Prosperity*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; Forthcoming. Charles W Wessner, Rapporteur.
- National Science Board. *Science and Engineering Indicators 2004*. Arlington, VA: National Science Foundation; 2004.
- National Science Board. *Science and Engineering Indicators 2006*. Arlington, VA: National Science Foundation; 2006.
- National Science Board. *Science and Engineering Indicators 2008*. Arlington, VA: National Science Foundation; 2008.
- National Science Foundation. *Science and Engineering Doctorate Awards: 2003*. Arlington, VA: National Science Foundation; 2004. NSF 05-300.
- Needham Joseph. *Science and Civilization in China*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1954–1986. (Five volumes.)
- Nelson RR. *National Innovation Systems: A Comparative Analysis*. New York: Oxford University Press; 1993.
- Nelson RR, Nelson K. *Technology, Institutions, and Innovation Systems*. *Research Policy*. 2002;31:265–272.
- Nelson RR, Rosenberg N. *Technical Innovation and National Systems, National Innovation Systems: A Comparative Analysis*. Nelson Richard R., editor. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 1993.
- Nelson RR, Winter SG. *An Evolutionary Theory of Economic Change*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press; 1982.
- Neuffer John. *China: Intellectual Property Infringement, Indigenous Innovation Policies, and Frameworks for Measuring the Effects on the U.S. Economy, Testimony to the United States International Trade Commission Investigation*. Jun 15, 2010.
- Nishimura, Kiyohiko G, Nakajima Takano, Kiyota Kojo. *Does the Natural Selection Mechanism Still Work in Severe Recessions? Examination of the Japanese Economy in the 1990s*. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*. 2003;58:53–78.
- Odagiri H. *University-Industry Collaboration in Japan: Facts and Interpretations*. In: Branscomb Lewis M, Kodama Fumio, Florida Richard., editors. *Industrializing Knowledge: University-Industry Linkage in Japan and the United States*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 1999.
- Odagiri H, Goto A. *The Japanese System of Innovation: Past, Present and Future*. In: Nelson RR, editor. *National Systems of Innovation*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 1993.
- Odagiri H, Goto A. *Technology and Industrial Development in Japan: Building Capabilities by Learning, Innovation and Public Policy*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 1996.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. *Boosting Innovation: The Cluster Approach*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 1999.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. *Managing National Innovation Systems*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 1999.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. *The New Economy: Beyond the Hype—The OECD Growth Project*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2001.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. *Social Sciences and Innovation*. Washington, DC: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2001.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. *Summary Report: Micro-policies for Growth and Productivity*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development; Oct, 2004. DSTI/IND(2004)7.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. *OECD Reviews of Innovation Policy: China*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2008.

- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Main Science and Technology Indicators. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2011.
- Orszag Peter, Kane Thomas. Funding Restrictions at Public Universities: Effects and Policy Implications. Brookings Institution Working Paper. Sep, 2003.
- Oughton Christine. Competitiveness in the 1990s. *The Economic Journal*. 1997;107(444):1486–1503.
- Oughton Christine, Landabaso Mikel, Morgan Kevin. The Regional Innovation Paradox: Innovation Policy and Industrial Policy. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2002;27(1)
- Owens William, Offley Edward. *Lifting the Fog of War*. Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press; 2001.
- Park WG, Ginarte JC. Intellectual Property Rights and Economic Growth. *Contemporary Economic Policy*. 1997 Jul;XV:51–61.
- Patel P, Pavitt K. National Innovation Systems: Why They are Important and How They Might Be Compared? *Economic Change and Industrial Innovation*. 1994
- Peck MJ, Levin RC, Goto Akira. Picking Losers: Public Policy Toward Declining Industries in Japan. In: Shoven JB, editor. *Government Policy Toward Industry in the United States and Japan*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press; 1988. pp. 165–239.
- Peek Joe, Rosengren Eric S. Unnatural Selection: Perverse Incentives and the Misallocation of Credit in Japan. *The American Economic Review*. 2005;95(4):114–1166.
- Penrose E. *The Economics of the International Patent System*. Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press; 1951.
- Perez Carlota. *Technological Revolutions and Financial Capital*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2002.
- Phan Phillip H, Siegel Donald S. Rensselaer Working Papers in Economics 0609. Troy, NY: Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute Department of Economics; 2006. The Effectiveness of University Technology Transfer: Lessons Learned from Qualitative and Quantitative Research in the U.S. and U.K.
- Phan Phillip H, Siegel Donald S, Wright Mike. Science Parks and Incubators: Observations, Synthesis and Future Research. *Journal of Business Venturing*. 2005;20(2):165–182.
- Phillimore J. Beyond the Linear View of Innovation in Science Park Evaluation: An Analysis of Western Australian Technology Park. *Technovation*. 1999;19(11):673–680.
- Polenske Karen, Rockler Nicolas, et al. NIST GCR 03-856. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2004. Closing the Competitive Gap: A Retrospective Analysis of the ATP 2mm Project.
- Porter ME. Clusters and the New Economics of Competition. *Harvard Business Review*. 1998;76(6):77–90. [[PubMed](#)]
- Porter ME, Sakakibara M. Competition in Japan. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*. 2004;18(1)
- Posen Adam. *Restoring Japan's Economic Growth*. Washington, DC: Peterson Institute for International Economics; 1998.
- Posen Adam S. Japan. In: Steil Benn, Victor David G, Nelson Richard R., editors. *Technological Innovation and Economic Performance*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press; 2001.
- Powell Jeanne, Moris Francisco. NISTIR 6917. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2002. Different Timelines for Different Technologies.
- President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology. *Sustaining the Nation's Innovation Ecosystems*. Washington, DC: Executive Office of the President; Jan, 2004.
- President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology. *Sustaining the Nation's Innovation System: Report on Information Technology Manufacturing and Competitiveness*. Washington, DC: Executive Office of the President; Jan, 2004.
- President's Information Technology Advisory Committee. *Cybersecurity: A Crisis of Prioritization, Report to the President*. Feb, 2005.
- PricewaterhouseCoopers. *China's Impact on the Semiconductor Industry: 2005 Update*. New York: PricewaterhouseCoopers; 2006.
- Procassini Andrew. *Competitors in Alliance: Industry Associations, Global Rivalries, and Business-Government Relations*. New York: Greenwood Publishing; 1995.
- Purvis G. Moving into the Real World. *Electronic Business*. Jul 1, 2002.
- Qiang Christine Zhen-Wei. *Broadband Infrastructure Investment in Stimulus Packages: Relevance for Developing Countries*. Washington DC: World Bank; 2009.

- Raduchel William. National Research Council. The End of Stovepiping. In: Wessner Charles W., editor. The Telecommunications Challenge: Changing Technologies and Evolving Policies. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2006.
- Reid TR. The United States of Europe: The New Superpower and the End of American Supremacy. New York: Penguin Press; 2004.
- Reiko Yamada. University Reform in the Post-massification Era in Japan: Analysis of Government Education Policy for the 21st Century. Higher Education Policy. 2001;14(4)
- Reuters. China Sees No Quick End to Economic Boom. Feb 21, 2006.
- Rich Ben. Skunkworks. New York: Back Bay Books; 1996.
- Rodrik Dani, Subramanian Arvind. From 'Hindu Growth' to Productivity Surge: The Mystery of the Indian Growth Transition. NBER Working Paper 10376. 2004.
- Romanainen Jari. The Cluster Approach in Finnish Technology Policy. In: Bergman Edward M, den Hertog Pim, Charles David., editors. Innovative Clusters: Drivers of National Innovation Systems; OECD Proceedings; Washington, DC: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2001. pp. 377–388.
- Romer Paul. Endogenous Technological Change. Journal of Political Economy. 1990;98:72–102.
- Rosenberg N, Nelson R. American Universities and Technical Advance in Industry. Research Policy. 1994;23:325–348.
- Rosenzweig R, Turlington B. The Research Universities and Their Patrons. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press; 1982.
- Rothaermel FT, Thursby MC. Incubator Firm Failure or Graduation? The Role of University Linkages. Research Policy. 2005;34(7):1076–1090.
- Rothaermel FT, Thursby MC. University-Incubator Firm Knowledge Flows: Assessing Their Impact on Incubator Firm Performance. Research Policy. 2005;34(3):302–320.
- Rowen Henry S, Maria Toyoda A. From Kiretsu to Start-ups: Japan's Push for High Tech Entrepreneurship, Asia-Pacific Research Center Working Paper. Stanford, CA: 2002.
- Ruegg Rosalie, Feller Irwin. NIST GCR 03-857. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2003. A Toolkit for Evaluating Public R&D Investment: Models, Methods, and Findings from ATP's First Decade.
- Ruttan Vernon W. Technology, Growth and Development: An Induced Innovation Perspective. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 2002.
- Ruttan Vernon W. Is War Necessary for Economic Growth, Military Procurement and Technology Development? New York: Oxford University Press; 2006.
- Ruttan Vernon W. Will Government Programs Spur the Next Breakthrough? Issues in Science and Technology. Winter. 2006.
- Rutten Roel, Boekema Frans. Innovation, Policy and Economic Growth: Theory and Cases. European Planning Studies. 2005;13(8)
- Rycroft Robert W, Kash Don E. Innovation Policy for Complex Technologies, Issues in Science and Technology. Fall. 1999.
- Saito Ken. Research on a New Concern: RIKEN Industrial Group. (In Japanese.), Jichosha. 1987.
- Sakakibara M, Branstetter L. Do Stronger Patents Induce More Innovation? Evidence from the 1988 Japanese Patent law Reforms. Rand Journal of Economics. 2001;32:77–100.
- Sakakibara M, Branstetter L. NIST GCR 02-830. Gaithersburg, MD: National Institute of Standards and Technology; 2002. Measuring the Impact of ATP-Funded Research Consortia on Research Productivity of Participating Firms, A Framework Using Both U.S. and Japanese Data.
- Sakamoto Kozo, Kondo Masayuki. "The Analysis of University-Industry Research Collaborations by Time Series and Corporate Characteristics." (In Japanese.). Development Engineering. 2004;10:11–26.
- Sallet J, Masterman J, Paisley E. The Geography of Innovation. Washington, DC: Center for American Progress; 2009.
- Sapolsky Harvey M. Science and the Navy—The History of the Office of Naval Research. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press; 1990. [[PubMed](#)]
- Saxenian AnnaLee. Regional Advantage: Culture and Competition in Silicon Valley and Route 128. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press; 1994.
- Schaffer Teresita. Building a New Partnership with India. Washington Quarterly. 2002;25(2):31–44.

- Scherer FM. U.S. Government Programs to Advance Technology. *Revue d'Economie Industrielle*. 2001;0(94):69–88.
- Science Committee of the Council for Science and Technology of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology. *Sciences Policy to Support Diversity in Research*. Kenkyuuno-tayousei wo-sasaeru Gakujutu-seisaku. 2005 Oct 13
- Scotchmer Suzanne. Protecting Early Innovators: Should Second-Generation Products Be Patentable? *Rand Journal of Economics*. 1996;27:322–331.
- Scotchmer Suzanne. *Innovation and Incentives*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 2004.
- Segal Adam. *China's Innovation Wall; Beijing's Push for Homegrown Technology*. Foreign Affairs. 2010.
- Shane S. *Academic Entrepreneurship*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing; 2004.
- Shang Yong. *Innovation: New National Strategy of China*. Presentation at Industrial Innovation in China; Levin Institute Conference. July 24–26. 2006.
- Shanghai Municipal Government. *Notice of the Shanghai Municipal Government Regarding Distributing the Outline of Shanghai's Intellectual Property Strategy (2004–2010)*. Sep 14, 2004.
- Shapiro Carl. *Navigating the Patent Thicket: Cross License, Patent Pools and Standard-Setting*. In: Jaffe Adam, Lerner Joshua, Stern Scott., editors. *Innovation Policy and the Economy*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 2001.
- Shearmur R, Doloreux D. *Science Parks: Actors or Reactors? Canadian Science Parks in their Urban Context*. *Environment and Planning*. 2000;32(6):1065–1082.
- Sheehan Jerry, Wyckoff Andrew. *Targeting R&D: Economic and Policy Implications of Increasing R&D Spending, DSTI/DOC(2003)8*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development; 2003.
- Shenzhen Daily. *Nation May Introduce Antimonopoly Law*. Dec 30, 2005.
- Sherwin Martin, Bird Kai. *American Prometheus: The Triumph and Tragedy of J. Robert Oppenheimer*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf; 2005.
- Shin Roy W. *Interactions of Science and Technology Policies in Creating a Competitive Industry: Korea's Electronics Industry*. *Global Economic Review*. 1997;26(4):3–19.
- Siegel Donald S, Waldman David, Link Albert. *Toward a Model of the Effective Transfer of Scientific Knowledge from Academicians to Practitioners: Qualitative Evidence from the Commercialization of University Technologies*. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*. 2004;21(1–2):115–142.
- Siegel Donald S, Westhead P, Wright M. *Assessing the Impact of Science Parks on Research Productivity: Exploratory Firm-Level Evidence from the United Kingdom*. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*. 2003;21(9):1357–1369.
- Simon Dennis, Cao Cong. *China's Emerging Technological Edge: Addressing the Role of High-End Talent*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2009.
- Skolnikoff Eugene B. *Knowledge Without Borders? Internationalization of the Research Universities*. *Daedalus*. 1993;122(4)
- Smith Kathlin. *The Role of Scientists in Normalizing U.S.-China Relations: 1965–1979*, Council on Library and Information Resources. 1998.
- Smits Ruud, Kuhlmann Stefan. *The Rise of Systemic Instruments in Innovation Policy*. *International Journal of Foresight and Innovation Policy*. 2004;1(1/2)
- Soete Luc G, ter Weel Bastiann J. *Innovation, Knowledge Creation and Technology Policy: The Case of the Netherlands*. *De Economist*. 1999 Sep;147(3)
- Sofouli E, Vonortas NS. *S&T Parks and Business Incubators in Middle-Sized Countries: The Case of Greece*. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2007;32(5):525–544.
- Solow Robert. *Growth Theory: An Exposition*. 2nd edition. New York: Oxford University Press; 2000.
- Solow Robert. *Toward a Macroeconomics of the Medium Run*. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. 2000 Winter;
- Spence Michael. *Market Signaling: Informational Transfer in Hiring and Related Processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press; 1974.
- Spencer William, Seidel TE. *National Research Council. International Technology Roadmaps: The U.S. Semiconductor Experience*. In: Jorgenson Dale W, Wessner Charles W., editors. *Productivity and Cyclicity in Semiconductors: Trends, Implications, and Questions*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2004.
- Spencer WJ, Wilson L, Doering R. *The Semiconductor Technology Roadmap*. *Future Fab International*. 2004:18.

- Springut Micah, et al. U.S.-China Economic and Security Review Commission; Jan, 2011. China's Program for Science and Technology Modernization: Implications for American Competitiveness.
- Stanford University. Inventions, Patents and Licensing: Research Policy Handbook, Document 5.1. Jul 15, 1999.
- State Council of the Peoples' Republic of China. Outline of the National Medium- and Long-term Program on Scientific and Technological Development (2006–2020). Feb 9, 2006.
- Statistics Bureau, Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications. Report on the Survey of Research and Development 2004, Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications. 2005.
- Stephan P. Educational Implication of University-Industry Technology Transfer. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2001;26:199–205.
- Sternberg R. The Impact of Innovation Centres on Small Technology-based Firms: The Example of the Federal Republic of Germany. *Small Business Economics*. 1990;2(2):105–118.
- Stiglitz Joseph. The Ethical Economist, *Foreign Affairs*. Council on Foreign Affairs; 11/12, 2005. Accessed at <<http://www.foreignaffairs.org>>.
- Stokes Donald E. Pasteur's Quadrant: Basic Science and Technological Innovation. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution Press; 1997.
- Strout E. Gift of a Book Was a Key to Intel Founder's Big Donation to City College of New York. *Chronicle of Higher Education*. 2005 Dec 2:A27.
- Su Yun-Shan, Hung Ling-Chun. Spontaneous vs. Policy-driven: The Origin and Evolution of the Biotechnology Cluster, *Technological Forecast and Social Change*. 2008.
- Swann GMP. Towards a Model of Clustering in High-Technology Industries. In: Swann GMP, Prevezer M, Stout D, editors. *The Dynamics of Industrial Clustering*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press; 1998.
- Talele Chitram J. Science and Technology Policy in Germany, India and Pakistan. *Indian Journal of Economics and Business*. 2003;2(1):87–100.
- Tanaka Nobua. Presentation at the International Forum on Technology Foresight and National Innovation Strategies; Seoul, Republic of Korea. November 4, 2005.
- Tassef G. The Economics of R&D Policy. Westport, CT: Quorum Books; 1997.
- Tassef G. Policy Issues for R&D Investment in a Knowledge-based Economy. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2004;29:153–185.
- Tassef G. *The Innovation Imperative*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2007.
- Teubal Morris. What Is the Systems Perspective to Innovation and Technology Policy and How Can We Apply It to Developing and Newly Industrialized Economies? *Journal of Evolutionary Economics*. 2002;12:1–2.
- Thelin J. *A History of American Higher Education*. Baltimore, MD: Johns Hopkins University Press; 2004.
- Thomas JR, Schacht WH. Patent Reform in the 110th Congress: Innovation Issues, Report for Congress. Washington, DC: Congressional Research Service; 2008. Order Code RL33996.
- Thursby J, Thursby M. Who is Selling the Ivory Tower? Sources of Growth in University Licensing. *Management Science*. 2002;48:90–104.
- Thursby J, Thursby M. Industry Perspectives on Licensing University Technologies: Sources and Problems. *AUTM Journal*. 2004;2000.
- U.S.-China Joint Commission on Commerce and Trade (JCCT). Outcomes on Major U.S. Trade Concerns. Washington, DC: The Office of the United States Trade Representative; 2005.
- U.S. Congress. Omnibus Trade and Competitiveness Act of 1988 (P.L. 100–418, codified in 15 U.S.C. 278n.) and later amended by the *American Technology Preeminence Act of 1991* (P.L. 102–245, codified in 15 U.S.C. 3701).
- U.S. Department of Commerce. Innovation Measurement: Tracking the State of Innovation in the American Economy, Report to the Secretary. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Commerce; Jan, 2008. Available at <<http://www.innovationmetrics.gov/Innovation%20Measurement%2001-08.pdf>>.
- U.S. General Accounting Office. Export Controls: Rapid Advances in China's Semiconductor Industry Underscore Need for Fundamental U.S. Policy Review. Washington, DC: U.S. General Accounting Office; Apr, 2002. GAO-020620.
- U.S. Small Business Administration. Small Business by the Numbers, Office of Advocacy. Washington, DC: U.S. Small Business Administration; Jun, 2004.
- Vaidyanathan G. Technology Parks in a Developing Country: The Case of India. *Journal of Technology Transfer*. 2008;33(3):285–299.

- Van Atta Richard. Energy and Climate Change Research and the DARPA Model. Presentation to the Washington Roundtable on Science and Public Policy; November 3. 2004.
- Van Atta Richard. Fifty Years of Innovation and Discovery, DARPA: 50 Years of Bridging the Gap. Arlington, VA: Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency; Apr, 2008.
- Van Atta Richard, et al. DARPA Technical Accomplishments. Alexandria, VA: Institute for Defense Analysis; 1991.
- Van Atta Richard, et al. DARPA Technological Accomplishments: An Historical Review of Selected DARPA Projects. Alexandria, VA: Institute for Defense Analysis; 1991.
- Van Atta Richard, Lippitz Michael. Overall Assessment. Vol. 1. Alexandria, VA: Institute for Defense Analysis; 2003. Transformation and Transition: DARPA's Role in Fostering an Emerging Revolution in Military Affairs.
- Van Looy Bart, Debackere K, Magerman T. Assessing Academic Patent Activity: The Case of Flanders. Leuven, Belgium: SOOS; 2005.
- Van Looy Bart, Ranga Marina, Callaert Julie, Debackere Koenraad, Zimmermann Edwin. Combining Entrepreneurial and Scientific Performance in Academia: Towards a Compounded and Reciprocal Matthew-effect? Research Policy. 2004;33(3):425–441.
- Vedovello C. Science Parks and University-Industry Interaction: Geographical Proximity between the Agents as a Driving Force. Technovation. 1997;17(9):491–502.
- Vervliet Greta. Science, Technology, and Innovation. Brussels, Belgium: Ministry of Flanders, Science and Innovation Administration; 2006.
- Vest C. 2005 Clark Kerr Lecture. Berkeley: University of California; Sep 13, 2005. Industry, Philanthropy and Universities-The Roles and Influences of the Private Sector in Higher Education.
- Veugelers Reinhilde, Larosse Jan, Cincera Michele, Carchon Donald, Kalenga-Mpala Roger. R&D Activities of the Business Sector in Flanders: Results of the R&D Surveys in the Context of the 3% Target, IWT-Studies. Brussels, Belgium: 2004.
- Wadhwa Vivek, Gereffi Gary. Framing the Engineering Outsourcing Debate. Durham, NC: Duke University; 2005.
- Walcott Susan M. Chinese Science and Technology Industrial Parks. Aldershot, UK: Ashgate Publishing; 2003.
- Waldrop M Mitchell. Complexity: The Emerging Science at the Edge of Order and Chaos. New York: Simon & Schuster; 1992.
- Waldrop M Mitchell. The Dream Machine. New York: Viking Press; 2001.
- Walsh J, Arora A, Cohen W. Research Tool Patent and Licensing and Biomedical Innovation, Patents in the Knowledge-Based Economy. Cohen W, Merrill S, editors. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2003.
- Walsh JP, Cohen WM. Does the Golden Goose Travel? A Comparative Analysis of the Influence of Public Research on Industrial R&D in the U.S. and Japan. Mimeo: 2004.
- Wang Changyong. IPR Sails Against Current Stream. Caijing Magazine. Oct 17, 2005. Available online at < <http://caijing.hexun.com>>.
- Wang Liwei. The Chinese Traditions Inimical to the Patent Law. Northwestern Journal of International Law and Commerce. 1993 Fall;
- Warsh David. Knowledge and the Wealth of Nations. New York: W. W. Norton; 2006. Chinese to Develop Sciences, Technology. The Washington Post. Feb 10, 2006. p. A16.
- Wen Jiang, Kobayashi Shinichi. Exploring Collaborative R&D Network: Some New Evidence in Japan. Research Policy. 2001;30:1309–1319.
- Wessner Charles W. Entrepreneurship and the Innovation Ecosystem. In: Audretsch David B, Grimm Heike, Wessner Charles W., editors. Local Heroes in the Global Village: Globalization and the New Entrepreneurship Policies. New York: Springer; 2005.
- Westhead P. New Owner-Managed Businesses in Rural and Urban Areas in Great Britain: A Matched Pairs Comparison. Regional Studies. 1995;29(4):367–380.
- Westhead P. R&D 'Inputs' and 'Outputs' of Technology-based firms Located On and Off Science Parks. R&D Management. 1997;27(1):45–61.
- Westhead P, Storey D. An Assessment of Firms Located On and Off Science Parks in the United Kingdom. London, UK: HMSO; 1994.
- Westhead P, Storey D. Financial Constraints on the Growth of High-Technology Small Firms in the U.K. Applied Financial Economics. 1997;7(2):197–201.
- Westhead P, Storey DJ, Cowling M. An Exploratory Analysis of the Factors Associated with the Survival of Independent High-Technology Firms in Great Britain. In: Chittenden F, Robertson

- M, Marshall I, editors. *Small Firms: Partnerships for Growth*. London, UK: Paul Chapman; 1995.
- Westhead P, Cowling M. Employment Change in Independent Owner-Managed High-Technology Firms in Great Britain. *Small Business Economics*. 1995;7(2):111–140.
 - Westhead P, Batstone S. Independent Technology-based Firms: The Perceived Benefits of a Science Park Location. *Urban Studies*. 1998;35(12):2197–2219.
 - The White House. Remarks by President Obamam, Prague. Apr 5, 2009.
 - Wiener Norbert. *Cybernetics or Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 1948.
 - World Bank. *Innovation Systems: World Bank Support of Science and Technology Development*. Goel Vinod Kumar., editor. Washington, DC: World Bank; 2004.
 - World Bank. *The Environment for Innovation in India, South Asia Private Sector Development and Finance Unit*. Washington, DC: World Bank; 2006.
 - World Bank International Finance Corporation. *Doing Business in 2006: Creating Jobs*. Washington, DC: International Bank for Reconstruction and Development; 2006.
 - World Trade Organization Working Party on the Accession of China. Report of the Working Party on the Accession of China. WT/MN(01)/3. Nov 10, 2001.
 - Wu Ching. China to Build 30 New Science and Technology Parks. *SciDev.net*. Apr 19, 2006.
 - Yan Dai. Anti-Monopoly Legislation on the Way. *China Daily*. Jun 18, 2004.
 - Yang Lei., editor. Chinese WAPI Delegation Quits Prague Meeting. *Xinhua*. Jun 8, 2006. Available at <<http://news.xinhuanet.com>>.
 - Yasuda T. “Seisakukinyuu no riyuu” (The Utilization of Public Finance), *Nippon no shinku kaigyou kigyuu (Startup Enterprises in Japan)*. Kustuna K, Yasuda T, editors. Hakutousha; 2005.
 - Yoshida Fujio. Preparation of Legal System for Capital Liberalization (Part 3), Panel Discussion in *Zaikei Shoho*. Jul 17, 1967.
 - Yoshida Junko. Grenoble Lure: Un-French R&D. *EE Times*. Jun 12, 2006.
 - Young John. Info Memo for Secretary of Defense Robert M. Gates, DoD Science and Technology Program. Aug 24, 2007.
 - Yukio Sato. The Structure and Perspective of Science and Technology Policy in Japan. In: Laredo Phillipe, Mustar Phillipe., editors. *Research and Innovation Policies in the New Global Economy: An International Comparative Analysis*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar; 2001.
 - Zachary G Pascal. *Endless Frontier: Vannevar Bush, Engineer of the American Century*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press; 1999.
 - Zeigler Nicholas J. *Governing Ideas: Strategies for Innovation in France and Germany*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press; 1997.
 - Zemin Jiang. Keynote Speech at the National Technological Innovation Conference. Aug 23, 1999. General Secretary of the Communist Party of China Central Committee.
 - Ziedonis RH, Hall BH. The Effects of Strengthening Patent Rights on Firms Engaged in Cumulative Innovation: Insights from the Semiconductor Industry. In: Libecap Gary., editor. *Entrepreneurial Inputs and Outcomes: New Studies of Entrepreneurship in the United States*. Volume 13 of *Advances in the Study of Entrepreneurship, Innovation, and Economic Growth*. Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier Science; 2001.
 - Zhang Chunlin, Zeng Douglas Zhihua, Mako William Peter, Seward James. *Promoting Enterprise-Led Innovation in China, 2009*. Washington, D. C: The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank; 2009.
 - Zheng Liang, Xue Lan. The evolution of China’s IPR system and its impact on the patenting behaviours and strategies of multinationals in China. *International Journal of Technology Management*. 2010;51